

**THEORETICAL ASSESSMENT OF CHROMIUM DI-
TELLURIDE AS AN ANODE FOR APPLICATION IN
LITHIUM ION BATTERY**

**A Thesis submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the
Award of Degree of**

BS

In

Physics

BY

HAFSA RAZA

REGISTRATION # 19001210021

Department of Physics

UNIVERSITY OF GUJRAT

Session 2019-23

Hafsa Raza

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

“In the name of Allah, most Gracious, most Merciful”

Firstly, I would like to thank my Allah Almighty for giving me success in every task in my life. And our beloved Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W) Who give us the importance of knowledge.

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(Hafsa Raza)

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my Parents and my supervisor Dr. Abdul Majid.

(HAFSA RAZA)

DECLARATION

I, am Hafsa Raza d/o Raza Hussain, roll # 19011510-031, BS Physics scholar, Department of Physics, Faculty of sciences, University of Gujrat, Pakistan, hereby solemnly declare that this thesis titled “Theoretical assessment of chromium di-telluride as an anode for application in lithium ion battery” is based on my genuine work and has not yet been submitted or published elsewhere. Furthermore, I shall not use this thesis for obtaining any other degree from this University or any other Institution.

I also understand that if evidence of plagiarism is found in this thesis at any stage, even after the award of the degree, the degree may be cancelled and revoked by the University.

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It is certified that Hafsa Raza d/o Raza Hussain, roll # 19011510-031, BS Physics scholar, Department of Physics, Faculty of sciences, University of Gujrat, Pakistan worked under my supervision and the above stated declaration is true to the best of my knowledge.

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THESIS COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

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ABSTRACT

In the pursuit of efficient and sustainable energy devices, rechargeable lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have emerged as a key component due to their high energy density, long lifespan, and good rate capability. Ongoing research aims to enhance the performance of LIBs, with a particular focus on the cathode, anode, and electrolyte. This study explores and compares the potential of utilizing MoTe_2 and CrTe_2 as a novel anode material for LIBs based on first-principles theoretical predictions. While CrTe_2 in its layered form demonstrates stability at high temperatures, it is unable to accommodate lithium ions without structural deformation in its pure stoichiometric state. The reaction of lithium with both stoichiometric and non-stoichiometric CrTe_2 is found to be endothermic, rendering them unsuitable for lithiation processes in LIBs. However, our investigation reveals that Li intercalation into the host, specifically in the presence of a Cr monovacancy, exhibits an exothermic process. Motivated by this observation, we conducted a detailed study of this system. Using a supercell configuration of structure, where x represents the lithium insertion level, we calculated an average lithium insertion voltage of 0.72 V and a theoretical capacity of $1744.84 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$. Furthermore, we examined the diffusion barrier encountered by lithium atoms during movement along the crystalline a -axis and c -axis. We found that the minimum energy path for lithium diffusion along the a -axis involves traversing between carbon atoms while linking hexagonal rings. Conversely, for motion along the c -axis, the route via hexagonal rings presents the lowest energy path. The reduced diffusion barrier observed in CrTe_2 suggests rapid movement of lithium ions, indicating the potential for fast-charging capabilities when CrTe_2 is employed as an anode material. This study highlights the promising prospects of utilizing CrTe_2 in LIBs and provides valuable insights into the structural and electrochemical properties of this system.

INTRODUCTION

Since its introduction by Sony in 1991, rechargeable lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have become the standard power source for portable electronic devices and electric vehicles (Agosta et al., 2021; Aras et al., 2022; Behara et al., 2021). Also regarded as the most promising choice for large-scale applications such as (hybrid) electric cars and short to medium-term stationary energy storage. Because of limited resources, the extensive use of fossil fuels (petroleum, coal, and gas) is currently the source of significant economic and political problems, even though the world's energy demand expected to increase over the next 20 years (Li et al., 2018). LIBs have demonstrated their significant advantages in terms of extended cycle life, high durability, high power density, and high energy density (Zhao et al., 2021). Commercialized Li-ion batteries currently use negative electrodes made of carbon or graphite, which provide high cycling performance, but graphite has a limiting theoretical capacity of $\sim 372 \text{mAhg}^{-1}$ and may be dangerous under certain circumstances. Tesla Company used graphite as an anode material in LIBs (Persichetti et al., 2016).

After graphene became experimentally available in 2004, layered materials such as graphene drew a lot of attention owing to their unique morphology and capacity to meet the adaptability, flexibility, and multi-functionality requirements of the upcoming nano-electronic industry (Liu et al., 2019). Graphene regarded as the marvel material of the twenty-first century, with astonishing properties such as conducting electricity better than copper, being impermeable to gases, being 70 percent stronger than steel, and being practically transparent (Shi et al., 2016). These properties provide graphene with seemingly limitless possibilities; the majority are currently not commercially feasible (Li et al., 2018; Panda et al., 2020).

Lithium titanate oxides (LTO), which practically employed as an anode material in lithium ion batteries, have a theoretical capacity of about 175mAhg^{-1} and are an ideal anode material for LIBs. LTO used as an anode material in LIBs in Yinlong battery technology (Persson et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2016). This business produces LTO battery cells in China. These battery cells can function in a large temperature range, charge quickly, and have a 30-year lifespan (Tan et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2016).

Consequently, a significant amount of study has done in recent years on the design of materials for their usage in devices for storing energy (Zhou et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2019). It is important to enhance the theoretical capacity of anode materials for LIBs because this is still far from meeting the present demand for large-capacity batteries. Owing to its substantial theoretical

capacity of 4200 mAhg^{-1} , silicon has received a lot of interest as a next-generation anode material (Borges et al., 2010; Khan et al., 2021).

The mineral calcium titanium oxide (CaTiO_3), which was the first perovskite crystal to be found and has the same crystal structure is known as a perovskite compound (Behara et al., 2021). A Russian mineralogist Lev Perovski is honored by the name of the mineral, which was found in the Ural Mountains of Russia by Gustav Rose in 1839 (Mitzi, 2019).

Layered materials meet these requirements and hence constitute an important class of electrode materials for anodes in LIBs (Xu & Jiang, 2020). 2D-layered anode materials are preferred because they have a large capacity to store lithium ions, and our research purpose on the electrodes (anode, cathode) is to try to search out the best material for LIBs (Ji et al., 2020; Katz, 2020).

The family of two-dimensional materials has grown to include a wide range of categories, such as transition metal oxides (TMOs), graphite, Xenes, MXenes; transition metal carbonates (TMCs), transition metal chalcogenides, and transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs). Most of these materials are serves as an electrode in lithium-ion batteries (Koster et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2022).

In order to meet the requirements for LIB anodes, new research is continually being conducted (Ji et al., 2020; Lu et al., 2022). The category of 2D material, transition metal oxides MX (M = transition metal and X = oxygen), due to its high theoretical capacity, is a promising anode material for lithium ion batteries (Borges et al., 2010).

Transition metal dichalcogenides have been considered the family (MX_2 M= transition metal and X= chalcogenide elements) promising anode materials for a variety of applications for decades, but their outstanding performance in demanding lithium-ion batteries has recently drawn attention (Zhu et al., 2019). These transition metal chalcogenides distinguished by their unique and organized two-dimensional lattice structure (X-M-X), in which the transition metal and chalcogenide periodically grouped in a hexagonal configuration (J. Wang et al., 2021). The hexagonal structure of TMDCs, which referred to as 2D materials rather than the atomically thin graphene, is not as thin as a single carbon atom (Sun et al., 2018).

Perovskites compounds has the general formula ABX_3 . A^{+2} and B^{+4} are positive metal cations, where A is usually alkaline earth metals i.e. Sr, Ca (s-block, Group-2A) and B is transition metals Fe, Ti, Ru (d-block). X^{-2} is an anion, where X is usually O and in rare case halogens F, Cl, Br, I (p-block, Group-7A). This displays the unit cell of ideal structure of perovskite (Hasan et al., 2022; Katz, 2020). The A-atom (blue sphere) that inside the octahedral pattern which has

12 coordinate sites and make bonds with oxygen in-plane, out-plane and along z-axis. We have eight octahedra in pink color that surrounded an A-atom and B-atom is present inside a octahedron which has only six coordinates (BX_6) with X-atoms (Panda et al., 2020; Persichetti et al., 2016).

There have been several reported 2D materials, such as graphene and numerous suitable anode materials for energy storage applications. Transition metal oxides (TMOs) including layered structures (Fe_2CO_3) transition metal carbides and nitrides (MXenes), such as Ti_2C and Ti_3CN , and transition metal dichalcogenides i.e. MoS_2 , $MoTe_2$, WS_2 and WSe_2 etc (X. Zhang et al., 2021).

TMDCs exhibit a high theoretical capacity in comparison to the graphene and commercially used anode material graphite (Khan et al., 2021). MoS_2 material of this family has a theoretical capacity of 669 mAhg^{-1} as an anode material for lithium-ion batteries, while WS_2 and $MoTe_2$ has a theoretical capacity of 590 mAhg^{-1} . They demonstrate excellent performance in electronic conductivity, mechanical properties like graphene and its stability of material depends upon the phases (1T, 1T', 2H) of the materials (Agosta et al., 2021; X. Zhang et al., 2021).

The heart of this research is to increase the theoretical capacity of anode materials. In family of transition metal dichalcogenides, MoS_2 is the flagship material because of its rich history and perfect 2D structure (Borges et al., 2010). Recently, molybdenum dichalcogenides have received a lot of interest due to their Mo lowered size as compared to W and 54th most abundant element in earth crust. Due to mineral resources, the industrial usage of Mo and Cr are now higher (C. Wang et al., 2021; X. Zhang et al., 2021). This improves Mo's commercial viability for upcoming energy storage applications. This is the primary reason for using molybdenum as a standard material $MoTe_2$ to test a novel material of this class TMDCs in more depth (Purbawati et al., 2020).

$SrRuO_3$ belongs to a widely known family ($Sr_{n+1}Ru_nO_{3n+1}$) of ruthenates and has an infinite layer of material ($n = \infty$). In the perovskite compound $SrRuO_3$, the Sr cation occupies the A site in the crystal structure, while the Ru cation occupies the B site. The O anion occupies the X site, forming a BO_6 octahedron around the Ru cation. Since the Sr cation has a larger radius than the Ru cation, it requires a larger space to be accommodated in the crystal structure (Koster et al., 2012; Lu et al., 2022). This results in an expansion of the unit cell, which leads to the Sr cation occupying the interstitial sites in the crystal structure. Specifically, the Sr cation occupies the 12-coordinate face-centered cubic (FCC) interstitial sites within the (001) planes of the perovskite structure. To visualize this, imagine the BO_6 octahedra formed by the Ru cations stacked on top of each other in a 3D lattice (Cao et al., 1997; Qin et al., 2003). The Sr cations then occupy the interstitial sites between these octahedra, forming a 3D network of corner-

sharing BO_6 octahedral with Sr cations in the interstices. The resulting crystal structure is known as a Ruddlesden-Popper phase, where the Sr cations are situated in the so-called "rock salt" layers, between the perovskite layers formed by the Ru-O octahedral (Qin et al., 2003; Yang, 2021). In the case of SrRuO_3 , the formula is $\text{A}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_7$, where A is Sr and B is Ru. This means that there are two perovskite layers in the structure (Ziese et al., 2019).

The structure of this family (TMDCs) attracts research into developing chalcogenide-based anode materials with transition metals since it has a high-performance anode used in the construction of lithium-ion battery technology. Chalogens (Te, S, and Se) offer greater electrical conductivity, which is crucial for energy storage applications. All TMDCs have a similar general structure; however, the material characteristics can vary greatly depending on the size and charge of the both materials. Because of their inherent similarities, TMDCs typically studied in tandem. The bilayer host material tested as a benchmark, 2H- MoTe_2 , exhibits a higher theoretical capacity of 305 mAhg^{-1} and the limited volume expansion after the geometrical optimization of the structure, which is in good agreement with the prior theoretical and experimental results. After getting motivation from this bilayer host material, we tested a novel bilayer 1T- CrTe_2 anode material for lithium ion batteries.

The structure of this family (TMDCs) attracts research into developing chalcogenide-based anode materials with transition metals since it has a high-performance anode used in the construction of lithium-ion battery technology. Chalogens (Te, S, and Se) offer greater electrical conductivity, which is crucial for energy storage applications. All TMDCs have a similar general structure; however, the material characteristics can vary greatly depending on the size and charge of the both materials. Because of their inherent similarities, TMDCs typically studied in tandem. The bilayer host material tested as a benchmark, 2H- MoTe_2 , exhibits a higher theoretical capacity of 305 mAhg^{-1} and the limited volume expansion after the geometrical optimization of the structure, which is in good agreement with the prior theoretical and experimental results.

1.1 Research Objectives

The basic purpose to study a host material as an anode in lithium ion batteries. The following is a list of the research objectives:

- To conduct comparison results between anodes, MoTe_2 and CrTe_2 as a benchmark and novel material respectively.
- To understand the lithiation and delithiation reaction mechanism in lithium ion batteries through the study of anode (electrode).

- To examine theoretical storage capacity, cycle stability, and rate capabilities of anode material in LIBs.
- My aim is to investigate that anode which has high theoretical capacity, for high charging and discharging rate and long life span.
- To find out that anode which has less volume expansion.

Lithium-ion batteries have a higher power and energy density compared to other sorts of batteries; they can store more energy in a smaller volume. They have a higher voltage compared to other types of batteries, which can be beneficial for certain applications. LIBs have long cycle life and low self-discharge rate, which makes them ideal for use in portable devices and electric vehicles. They are also considered to be safer compared to other types of batteries, due to the use of a solid electrolyte that reduces the risk of thermal runaway. While the cost of lithium-ion batteries has come down over time, magnesium-ion and sodium-ion batteries are still more expensive to produce at scale compared to lithium-ion batteries

1.2 Research Problem

The problem is to find that anode for LIBs, which has high theoretical capacity, low volume expansion and high conductivity. These are the three main problems that faced while using materials as an anode in lithium ion batteries. Graphite is commercially used anode material, it has high conductivity and low volume expansion. The main issues in this material is that low storage capacity and 400-500 cycles. On the other hand, Silicon has problem of volume expansion round about 400%. Iron oxides (FeO) has high theoretical capacity approximately 1000 mAhg⁻¹ with high volume expansion. Our target is to find out that anode material which has layered 2D structure, high theoretical capacity, low volume expansion and high conductivity.

1.3 Planned Strategy

All plan of research were execute according to computational method, list of calculations, strategies and approaches to solve the problem that mentioned above.

1.4 Expected Outcomes

Intercalation of lithium atom into the structure of CrTe₂ in order to make the new compound then we use this compound as the electrode material. The estimation of this electrode material performance for high diffusion rate of lithium“ high conductivity and safer chemistry. Not only are these outcomes achieved but also the detailed study consequent upon additional findings, which are reflected in conclusions, part of chapter 4. The geometrical optimization done for the relaxation of all atoms in the host structure for investigation of structural properties.

Next, we performed the single point calculation for studying the electronic properties and for plotting graphs of TDOS and PDOS. Before performing the lithiation, we locate the five favorable intercalation sites for host materials that will be help for inserting lithium into it. Then, we moved toward the foremost task that is lithiation of anode material for checking its theoretical capacity. First, we performed all lithiation process on benchmark material MoTe₂. After it, we determined the theoretical storage capacity of this anode material. Surprisingly, it matched with the prior theoretical results. However, we tested a novel anode material CrTe₂, performed a lithiation process on it, and find out its theoretical capacity. After finding out theoretical capacity and intercalation stable sites, our main aim is to find out a diffusion path of lithium atoms. This calculation carried out through the NEB and it will be helpful for checking the electrochemical performance of rechargeable batteries. By using a formula that mentioned (equation-3), we plotting a voltage profile for both the host materials and then compared them. This voltage profile tells us the stability, cycling rate, charging and discharging voltage and maintenance time of the material through the curve.

1.5 Why choose MoTe₂ material as a benchmark?

Graphene is used as an anode in Li-ion batteries due to its high electrical conductivity, theoretical storage capacity is 744 mAhg⁻¹ and high surface area. The high electrical conductivity allows for efficient transfer of electrons during battery discharge and charge cycles. The high surface area of graphene provides more space for lithium ions to be stored, leading to a higher capacity for energy storage compared to other anode materials. Additionally, the mechanical stability of graphene allows for repeated expansion and contraction of the anode during battery cycling, leading to improved cycle life for the battery. These unique properties make graphene an attractive material for energy storage devices such as alkali ion batteries, especially lithium ion batteries, and super capacitors. Graphene is a two-dimensional material made up of carbon atoms organized in a hexagonal network. The carbon atoms in graphene are sp² hybridized, each carbon atom interacts strongly with its neighbors through three covalent bonds, while the fourth electron is in the p orbital, forming a π-bond. This strong covalent bonding gives graphene its high mechanical strength and makes it an ideal material for many applications in electronics, energy storage, and other fields. Graphene and MoTe₂ are both two-dimensional (2D) materials with layered structures, but they have some differences in terms of their chemical composition and crystal structure. Graphene and MoTe₂ have a layered structure, with each layer being composed of a repeating arrangement of atoms. Both materials have a hexagonal arrangement of atoms, which gives them a similar appearance when viewed at the atomic scale. Graphene is composed of carbon atoms only, while MoTe₂ is composed of Mo and Te atoms. Graphene has a hexagonal crystal structure with sp² hybridized carbon atoms, while 2H-MoTe₂ has a layered crystal structure with Te atoms sandwiched between layers of Mo

atoms. Graphene has strong covalent bonds between its carbon atoms, while MoTe₂ has a mixture of covalent and metallic bonds between its Mo and Te atoms. Despite these differences, both graphene and MoTe₂ have unique properties that make them useful for an application in lithium ion batteries.

1.6 Why was bilayer CrTe₂ selected for comparison studies with MoTe₂?

The comparison study of MoTe₂ and bilayer CrTe₂ for lithium-ion batteries is of interest because both materials have the potential to be used as anode materials in LIBs due to their unique properties. Transition metal dichalcogenides have high theoretical capacities for energy storage, making them promising materials for use as anodes in LIBs. Comparing the properties of MoTe₂ and bilayer CrTe₂ can enlighten/highlight/inform the development of new TMDs-based anodes with improved performance and stability. Both the host materials MoTe₂ and bilayer CrTe₂ have unique electronic properties, such as their layered crystal structure and transition metal composition, which can affect their ability to store and release lithium ions. Comparing the properties of these two materials can provide insights into how TMDs can be optimized for use as anodes in LIBs. Overall, the comparison study of MoTe₂ and bilayer CrTe₂ for lithium-ion batteries is important for advancing our understanding of transition metal dichalcogenides as anode materials and for the development of new anodes with improved performance and stability. After execution of the research, it is to mention that the problem addressed in true letter and spirit. The implementation of entire research strictly focused to address the problem, which can be viewed from the conclusions given in the end of chapter 4.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

As there is a huge shortage of energy storage devices today, researchers are working to replace fossil fuels with alternative energy sources like wind and solar energy. Several materials investigated in order to exploit these sources, with a focus on cheap cost and high-energy storage. One of the most practical forms of energy storage is the lithium ion battery, which has a simplistic chemistry (L. Zhang et al., 2021).

2.1. Cathode and Anode in LIBs

The basic three components of a lithium ion battery are an anode and a cathode, as well as an electrolyte, which is a liquid solution through which the lithium ions travel from anode to cathode or cathode to anode (Klein et al., 2021). Graphite is typically utilized as the anode and transition metal oxides are typically used as the cathode (Xu & Jiang, 2020). These materials are well-known for having the maximum structural stability following the lithium atom insertions. LiCoO_2 , LiMn_2O_4 , and LiFePO_4 are the most often utilized cathode materials nowadays, while graphite-based compounds are primarily employed as anode materials in lithium ion batteries (Li et al., 2021). Lithium has a graphite diffusion barrier of 10^{-12} and 10^{-6} , but since large power densities cannot be achieved with these values, the diffusion barrier must be improved (Borges et al., 2010). There is currently a lot of research being done that focuses on replacing graphite with other practical materials that can generate high capacity and power density. Many studies are being conducted right now that concentrate on finding realistic alternatives to graphite that can provide energy with high capacity and power density (Jiao et al., 2020). Additionally, lithium metal has the potential to create dendrites, which can result in a short circuit and the battery ceasing to function. Anode materials that can offer high capacity, high power density, and safer chemistry at high temperatures are desperately needed in this situation. Li metal cannot be employed as an electrode material as a result (Li et al., 2021). To address the shortcomings mentioned above, many researchers are working to create materials related to carbon. There are carbon nanofibers, carbon nanotubes, transition metal oxides, tin oxides, and silicon oxides among other things in those materials, but the advancements as a whole have not yet been made using carbon-related materials (Persson et al., 2010). Lithium intercalation transition metal dichalcogenides research. Low voltage is recommended for anode materials, and it has been discovered that MoX_2 and WX_2 can be utilized as anode materials since they have low voltage and consequently high capacity and good conductivity (Zhao et al., 2021). It has been discovered that the voltage duration in a material is caused by the charge transfer from cation to anion. The rate performance of lithium can be improved in these host materials for Li intercalation as anode because the diffusion barriers for WS_2 and WSe_2 are

discovered to be lower than those for other transition metals (Aras et al., 2022). Lithium ions flow from the anode, which is the negative electrode, to the cathode, which is the positive electrode, when the battery is being discharged. The charging mechanism exhibits the opposite of this behavior (Liu et al., 2022). The intercalation takes place after the Li ions have passed through the electrolyte and then intercalate on the host structure's corresponding minimum energy point. In order to prevent short circuits between the cathode and anode, the electrolyte region between them is really constructed of a porous substance (Dou & Fyta, 2020). There are carbon nanofibers, carbon nanotubes, transition metal oxides, tin oxides, and silicon oxides among other things in those materials, but the advancements as a whole have not yet been made using carbon-related materials (Liu et al., 2019). Lithium intercalation transition metal dichalcogenides research. Low voltage is recommended for anode materials. The battery's entire mechanism is shown in the diagram (Purbawati et al., 2020).

Figure-2.1 Mechanism of Lithium ion batteries (Goodenough & Park, 2013).

We will now give a quick overview of disruption which serves as the driving force for our research.

2.1.1 CrTe₂ potential as an electrode

Nowadays, there is a larger need for safe chemistry in the battery business that can be used in electrical vehicles as well as remaining stable across a wide temperature range (Meng et al., 2021). These parameters can be met by rechargeable batteries, but there is still a lot of room for development, particularly with regard to the electrodes thermal conductivity, broad band gap semiconductor, and high blocking voltage (Zhou et al., 2022). Despite all of these benefits, CrTe₂ crystal structure still has significant drawbacks, such as crystal flaws, which prevent it from being primarily employed in power electronics (Nie et al., 2023). Despite all of these benefits, CrTe₂ crystal structure still has significant drawbacks, such as crystal flaws, which

prevent it from being primarily employed in power electronics. Graphene is used as an anode in Li-ion batteries due to its high electrical conductivity, theoretical storage capacity is 744 mAhg^{-1} and high surface area (Wang et al., 2009). The high electrical conductivity allows for efficient transfer of electrons during battery discharge and charge cycles. The high surface area of graphene provides more space for lithium ions to be stored, leading to a higher capacity for energy storage compared to other anode materials (Klein et al., 2021). Additionally, the mechanical stability of graphene allows for repeated expansion and contraction of the anode during battery cycling, leading to improved cycle life for the battery (Goodenough & Park, 2013). These unique properties make graphene an attractive material for energy storage devices such as alkali ion batteries, especially lithium ion batteries, and super capacitors (Li et al., 2018). Graphene is a two-dimensional material made up of carbon atoms organized in a hexagonal network. The carbon atoms in graphene are sp^2 hybridized, each carbon atom interacts strongly with its neighbors through three covalent bonds, while the fourth electron is in the p orbital, forming a π -bond (Jiao et al., 2020). This strong covalent bonding gives graphene its high mechanical strength and makes it an ideal material for many applications in electronics, energy storage, and other fields. Graphene and MoTe_2 are both two-dimensional (2D) materials with layered structures, but they have some differences in terms of their chemical composition and crystal structure (Panda et al., 2020).

Graphene and MoTe_2 have a layered structure, with each layer being composed of a repeating arrangement of atoms (Persichetti et al., 2016). Both materials have a hexagonal arrangement of atoms, which gives them a similar appearance when viewed at the atomic scale. Graphene is composed of carbon atoms only, while MoTe_2 is composed of Mo and Te atoms (Grinberg et al., 2004). Graphene has a hexagonal crystal structure with sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms, while MoTe_2 has a layered crystal structure with Te atoms sandwiched between layers of Mo atoms (Nitta et al., 2015). Graphene has strong covalent bonds between its carbon atoms, while 2H-MoTe_2 has a mixture of covalent and metallic bonds between its Mo and Te atoms. Despite these differences, both graphene and MoTe_2 have unique properties that make them useful for an application in lithium ion batteries. The comparison study of MoTe_2 and bilayer CrTe_2 for lithium-ion batteries is of interest because both materials have the potential to use as anode materials in LIBs due to their unique properties (Li et al., 2018). Transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) have high theoretical capacities for energy storage, making them promising materials for use as anodes in LIBs. Comparing the properties of MoTe_2 and bilayer CrTe_2 can enlighten/highlight/inform the development of new TMDs-based anodes with improved performance and stability (Liu et al., 2022). Both the host materials MoTe_2 and bilayer CrTe_2 have unique electronic properties, such as their layered crystal structure and transition metal composition, which can affect their ability to store and release lithium ions.

Comparing the properties of these two materials can provide insights into how TMDs can be optimized for use as anodes in LIBs (Meng et al., 2021).

2.2. Favorable intercalation sites

Here, we have discussed about many structures that depend on structure.

2.2.1 Silicates

$\text{Li}_2\text{FeSiO}_4$ with the space group Pmn21, the first substance in the silicate family. Here, we will discuss about the structural locations of Li_2MSiO_4 in which both the transition metals and Si form a tetrahedral arrangement with shared corners (Cao et al., 1997). The Li ions are intercalated and can diffuse freely in between these corners. Because they are intercalated, the Li ions can freely diffuse in between these corners. Here, the layered, zigzag form takes shape. DFT calculations show that one Li ion has a capacity of 166mAh/g, and when two Li ions are introduced into the system, the capacity increases and rises to 333mAh/g. Additionally, this material is created experimentally using a variety of techniques, including hydrothermal, sol-gel, and microwave solvothermal processes (Koster et al., 2012). This material has excellent capacity and substantially improved power density efficiency. Its most well-known benefit is that the diffusion barrier will be low in the presence of this material, allowing for good working rates to be reached. Up to five lithium atoms per formula unit, the adsorption energies are also negative. For the first time ever, this material was synthesized experimentally using the sol-gel method. LiFeSO_4 whose unit cell is triclinic and has the space group P1, is the second substance in the silicate family that we address here (Li et al., 2018; Persson et al., 2010). This information has been discussed in two sections. The Fe atom occupies the octahedral site in the favorite phase, which is the first. The atoms in this phase of FeO_3F_2 are all working together to form a chain-like substance (Zhou et al., 2022).

And the remaining SO_4 atoms connect with that 1D chain-like material, sharing the octahedral chain of the atoms mentioned before. The tetrahedral sites in this structure seem more relaxed to the Li atom than any other site. Additionally, this Li atom is located towards the corner of the second SO_4 group and the F-O_4 group's edge. In these kinds of structures, it was first claimed that the Li atoms occupy half the sites in the first group and half the sites in the second group. However, further research reveals that the Li atoms only occupy sites in one group (Purbawati et al., 2020). The structural analysis of this structure reveals that it is also identical to Li_2MSiO_4 with Fe and the transition metal creates a tetrahedral arrangement with sharing of corners, and the lithium can be positioned on the tetrahedral sites between these corners sharing places. This structure creates a one-dimensional chain along the direction [001], and Li atoms can easily diffuse along these places (Khan et al., 2021). These structures' second phase, which belongs

to the $C2/c$ space group, has the same octahedral sites for the Fe atom as they had in the first phase. These two structures that make up this trip lite structure differ significantly from one another. In the octahedral structure of MO_4F_2 , the Fe atoms form an arrangement of atoms that is similar to cis, and this octahedral arrangement of atoms creates a zigzag chain that is distinct from the first phase previously stated (Liu et al., 2022). The O-O and Fe-Fe bonds that are created in these two distinct zigzag chains complement one another.

Figure-2.2 Structure of silicates (Borges et al., 2010).

2.2.2 Transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs)

In these formations, the atoms are arranged in an octahedral pattern or in triangular patterns by pairing six chalcogen atoms with every transition metal atom. These TMDs structures go through two distinct stages that depend on the stacking and symmetry of the structures (Jiao et al., 2020). These phases are known as the T and H phases. While the transition metal chalcogenides' layers in the 1T phase are stacked in an AA pattern, they are stacked in an AB pattern in the 2H phase. As it generates the same environment for lithium intercalation and can be easily understood from merely these two phases, the 3R phase is not covered here (Goodenough & Park, 2013). Both the octahedral and the tetrahedral sites for Li intercalation are present in these two phases, as seen in the figure below. Due to its large surface area, the octahedral site has been found by DFT studies to have the lowest energy site, making it the most suitable for Li intercalation (Ziese et al., 2019). According to observations, this location contains the least energy of any TMD, making it the most advantageous for TMD patients. Second place is the tetrahedral sites have higher energies than octahedral ones because to their low coordination numbers and the lack of space they provide for Li to unwind in the host structure (Zhou et al., 2022). As a result, lithium will relax here with more energy than it would at an octahedral location. Thus, only the octahedral site is taken into account for Li intercalation

in TMDs, and the voltage profile and capacity are estimated using this octahedral site. These TMDs' layered nature results in volume expansion after Li intercalation, a problem that affects all electrode materials (X. Zhang et al., 2021).

Figure-2.3 Structure of transition metal dichalcogenides (Gupta et al., 2015).

2.2.3 Carbonaceous

Since the early 1980s, when interest in Li-GIC began to grow, lithium intercalated graphite has been utilized extensively in lithium ion batteries. Although it was formerly utilized as a cathode in the electro-winning of aluminum. Among carbonaceous materials, graphite is renowned for having three distinct polytype belonging to the space groups P63/mc, P/63mmc, and R3m (Gupta et al., 2015).

Figure-2.4 Structure of Carbonaceous (Zhang et al., 2020).

Here, we talk about the P/63mmc polytype, which is 7meV/atom more energetic than AA but is more stable in AB stacking. Here, we talk about the P/63mmc polytype, which is 7meV/atom more energetic than AA but is more stable in AB stacking. When compared to AA stacking, which requires an interlayer spacing of 3.58 Å, the AB stacking sequence is more stable at 3.42 Å (Zhou et al., 2012). Equivalent locations in the structure serve as intercalation sites for lithium atoms. Sites in this polytype of graphite. These are the three locations where lithium can

intercalate and diffuse readily, changing the semi-metal nature of graphite into one with a metallic character. The most frequent stages are stage 1 and stage 2, and additional stages are not theoretically conducted because of the computationally expensive nature of this event (Agosta et al., 2021). In stage 1, lithium is added to every layer; there will be no layers that are vacant or free of lithium. Lithium will not be deposited in every layer in stage 2 but rather at the interface of two layers. The system will have both odd and even stages, so one must be careful when dealing with these two (Jiao et al., 2020). For instance, when there is even staging, lithium will be placed on the same sites in the layers, but when there is odd staging, lithium won't be placed there; instead, the sites must be different from one another to avoid repulsions in these situations between the lithium atoms (Lin et al., 2021). Although it was formerly utilized as a cathode in the electro-winning of aluminum, graphite is best recognized for its application as an anode in LIBs. For instance, when there is even staging, lithium will be placed on the same sites in the layers, but when there is odd staging, lithium won't be placed there; instead, the sites must be different from one another to avoid repulsions in these situations between the lithium atoms (X. Zhang et al., 2021).

2.2.4 Graphene

2D material with sp^2 hybridization and pi-bonding in its structure, graphene may create high conductivity and is now used in LIBs because it allows electrons to move freely along these bonds (Zhou et al., 2012). Three places in the structure are available for the adsorption of lithium, and two-unit cells are used in the simulation. The lattice constants for the optimized geometry are 4.26 Å and 4.92 Å. It is the measured bond length between two C atoms (Zhang et al., 2020). The three sites are H site, which is situated between the hexagonal rings, B site, or bridge site, and the top site, or T site. After optimization, it was discovered that the H site, where the Li atom has the lowest energy, is where it feels the most free. And it has been noted that, in comparison to other sites, the height calculated from the Li to H site is the lowest (Klein et al., 2021). The site with the shortest height indicates that the Li interaction with the C atom is greatest there, and as a result, the energy is lowest there following relaxation. The observed heights at the H site are 1.64 Å and -2.53 Å, the T site is 1.85 Å and -2.13 Å, and the B site is 1.84 Å and correspondingly -2.17 Å. It has been observed that, following Li intercalation, the first unit cell, in which there is only one Si atom and all other C atoms are present, has a higher capacity than the second example, in which there are two Si atoms present in the formula unit. It is the measured bond length between two C atoms (Persichetti et al., 2016). The three sites are H site, which is situated between the hexagonal rings, B site, or bridge site, and the top site, or T site. After optimization, it was discovered that the H site, where the Li atom has the lowest energy, is where it feels the most free (Persson et al., 2010). And it has been noted that, in comparison to other sites, the height calculated from the Li to H site is the lowest. It is the

measured bond length between two C atoms. The three sites are H site, which is situated between the hexagonal rings, B site, or bridge site, and the top site, or T site. After optimization, it was discovered that the H site, where the Li atom has the lowest energy, is where it feels the most free (Shi et al., 2016). And it has been noted that, in comparison to other sites, the height calculated from the Li to H site is the lowest. The site with the shortest height indicates that the Li interaction with the C atom is greatest there, and as a result, the energy is lowest there following relaxation (Wang et al., 2009).

Figure-2.5 Structure of graphene (Li et al., 2021).

2.2.5 Oxides

The space group $Fd\bar{3}m$ of lithium cobalt oxide, which has a rhombohedral structure, is a family of spinel structures (Li et al., 2021). Due to its unique structural characteristics and the size and shape of its crystals, this material has been extensively used as a cathode material in LIBs. Here, the cubic structure is formed when the material has been experimentally prepared at low temperatures below 500K (Meng et al., 2021). Furthermore, the material becomes rhombohedral with a layered structure $R\bar{3}m$ when it is manufactured at high temperatures above 500K (Ma et al., 2022). The layered structure of the rhombohedral structure includes the lithium atom intercalated with oxygen anions. These structures are typically referred to as the LT (low temperature) LiCoO_2 and the HT (high temperature) LiCoO_2 (Li et al., 2018). This particular structure generates the ABCABC stacking pattern with cobalt and lithium intercalated in the same layer. In this structure, lithium and cobalt atoms are intercalated with a difference of one oxygen layer between the layers of oxygen, which serve as anions in this structure and lithium as cations in this structure (Liu et al., 2019). On the octahedral sites of this structure, Co forms

a strong connection with O. In a similar manner, the oxygen atom and lithium atom are intercalated on the octahedral sites in this cathode material. This substance is organized with lithium, oxygen, and cobalt in the AB stack (J. Wang et al., 2021).

Figure-2.6 Structure of oxides (Lu et al., 2022).

Because these qualities heavily depend on the structure, the particular arrangement of atoms causes the smallest energy to stable with maximal charge delocalization. The second substance is LiNiO_2 , which has a hexagonal lattice with the space group $R\bar{3}m$ and Li, Ni, and O respectively (Persichetti et al., 2016). The structure with six carbon atoms also contains an octahedral site for the Ni atom. The octahedral arrangement between the Ni and O_6 is deformed after Li intercalation, as shown by the structural optimization, which also reveals that the structure is affected after Li intercalation (L. Zhang et al., 2021). The Co atom is partially incorporated with Ni in the structure to avoid this deformation. Due to the new bond lengths discovered in the structure after the Co atom was added, the bond lengths that were previously short and long changed, reducing the distortion. The structure with six carbon atoms also contains an octahedral site for the Ni atom (Li et al., 2021). The octahedral arrangement between the Ni and O_6 is deformed after Li intercalation, as shown by the structural optimization, which also reveals that the structure is affected after Li intercalation. The Co atom is partially incorporated with Ni in the structure to avoid this deformation. Due to the new bond lengths discovered in the structure after the Co atom was added, the bond lengths that were previously short and long changed, reducing the distortion (Agosta et al., 2021). The Co atom is partially incorporated with Ni in the structure to avoid this deformation. Due to the new bond lengths discovered in the structure after the Co atom was added, the bond lengths that were previously short and long changed, reducing the distortion (Ma et al., 2022).

2.2.6 Phosphates

Lithium iron phosphate, a member of the olivine family, is one of the crucial electrode materials and is regarded as the best reversible cathode material that can be used in electric equipment and automobiles (Agosta et al., 2021). This kind of structure exhibits a reductive insertion-like behavior in which the phases of the two coexisting states, LiFePO_4 and FePO_4 , throughout the transition. This structure formula is Li_xFePO_4 , and it has three distinct lattice parameters and the space group Pbnm (Cao et al., 1997).

Figure-2.7 Structure of phosphates (Lu et al., 2022).

2.2.7 Borophene

In order to produce a heterostructure for the adsorption of lithium, a 2×2 super cell of BP and a 4×4 super cell of Borophene are used. After optimization, 2.75 \AA of interlayer gap was discovered between these two 2D layers (Lu et al., 2022). The heterostructure of BP layers are closer together than this interlayer spacing. The energy discovered is equivalent to 0.05 eV/atom , which is the exothermic reaction, making it possible to determine whether this reaction is exothermic or endothermic (Yang, 2021). To improve the concentration of lithium, it is first important to identify the optimal lithium location in this heterostructure. Three locations are taken into account for one Li intercalation: first, the outside of BP, second, the outside of Borophene, and third, between the two layers. The reaction is most favorable for Li intercalation when the energy is more negative, and it is discovered that between the layers, the energy is more negative than it is elsewhere. In Li/P/B and P/B/Li , two adsorption sites have been identified: one is on top of P and is designated T_P , while the other is on top of B and is designated T_B (Ma et al., 2022). The adsorption energy in these two sites is 2.28 eV and 2.87 eV , respectively, which is lower than the BP heterostructure adsorption energies that have been observed. It is discovered that the top sites of the BP and Borophene have lower adsorption energies than the bridge site and hexagonal ring. It is discovered that the B-B bonds in the midst of these bonds have a very low adsorption energy, indicating that the conditions for lithium adsorption at this site are significantly more favorable than those at other sites. This site has an

energy of -2.83 eV (Wang et al., 2016). With a lithiation energy of -2.80 eV, it is discovered that Li adsorption between the two layers is stable on the top site of the B atom and on the bridge- or bond-centered site of the BP (Liu et al., 2019).

2.2.8 Lithium titanate Oxide (LTO)

Lithium titanate oxide ($\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$) can be used as an anode material in lithium-ion batteries. Lithium-ion batteries consist of an anode that is LTO and a cathode LMO (Lithium titanate oxide) (LiMn_2O_4) or NCM. Graphite is used as an anode in conventional batteries, but due to the increase in demand for lithium-ion batteries (Koster et al., 2012). Our main purpose is to increase its performance of charging and discharging rates. For this, we used alternative promising material that is LTO. In 1980, when researching superconductors then LTO was found. After studying, it was found that LTO is a zero-strain material. LTO material has high charging and discharging rate (Ma et al., 2022). It shows thermal stability. LTO has a very different structure from graphite. Oxygen is in red spheres and Titanium is in grey spheres. They are tightly bound to each other. The bonding between the oxygen and titanium is not disturbed when the lithium ions (Li^+) leave and enter into the molecules. Lithium is in purple spheres, they can move into the structure. Lithium also moves freely in graphite layers (L. Zhang et al., 2021). The characteristics of LTO (150 Ah kg^{-1} , Voltage 1.55 V) are excellent power ability, long life-span, high stability and good safety costly compared to graphite anode, spinel structure, space group ($\text{Fd}\bar{3}m$), during cycling the lattice parameter changes 0.1% (8.35 to 8.35 Å) (Ranjan et al., 2019). But graphite layers are simple. LTO layers are complicated and convoluted in the 3-dimensional pathway. For this, we used alternative promising material that is LTO (lithium titanate oxide). In 1980, when researching superconductors then LTO was found. After studying, it was found that LTO is a zero-strain material (Purbawati et al., 2020).

Figure-2.8 Structure of Lithium titanate oxide (Persichetti et al., 2016).

In the conventional lithium-ion batteries, we used graphite as an anode. Due to several problems like low storage capacity, less interactional voltage, and formation of dendrites, we want to replace an alternative anode material (Cao et al., 1997). A promising material is LTO which has high intercalation and extraction rate and shows many properties like thermal stable, Zero-

strain property (no changes in the size of lattice parameter, sometimes change may be possible less than 0.1%), and nano-particle size. One thing is to remember that the electrode does not only depend on material properties but also dependence on the interface between the electrode and electrolyte. Because Li^+ passes through the electrolyte (Ji et al., 2020). Lithium titanate has low conductivity (10^{-12} to $10^{-13} \text{ Scm}^{-1}$). LTO is found in the form of nano-materials. To enhance its conductor doping was performed with tetravalent cations (Mg^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+}). After practical testing of LMO/LTO cell, it was found that a gas is produced inside the battery that exerts internal pressure and also forces the electrodes to separate from each other. One thing is to remember that the electrode does not only depend on material properties, it is also dependent on the interface between the electrode and electrolyte. Because Li^+ passes through the electrolyte (Ma et al., 2022). LiPF_6 is a salt that is used as an electrolyte. When electrolyte dissolves in solution then disassociation of ions (Li^+ , PF_6^-) occurs. The solution of electrolyte is in equilibrium with the (Li^+ , PF_6^- , LiF , PF_5). According to Lewis acid-base theory, PF_5 is a strong Lewis acid. This strong acid starts to decompose the carbonates in the electrolyte and produced the gases like carbon dioxide (CO_2) and Carbon monoxide (CO). When reacts PF_5 water in the electrolyte then also produced hydrofluoric acid (HF). Then HF diffused the Mn^{+2} layer from the surface of the lithium manganese oxide (LiMn_2O_4). LTO/LMO produced an unexpected amount of gas during the process. LTO produces a higher amount of gas with LMO other than cathode material like LFP etc (Ma et al., 2022). LTO has a very low theoretical capacity 175 mAhg^{-1} . We can increase its capacity by changing its electrochemical properties. Lithium titanate has low conductivity. LTO is found in the form of nano-materials. This is the manufacturing company of LTO cells in China. These battery cells have a long life span of up to 30 years, are fast charging, safe, and operate at extreme temperatures (Qin et al., 2003). In the above discussion, we used mainly two transition metals that are titanium and manganese. Firstly, titanium is a central element of LTO. If we replace any other transition metal with replacement of titanium. They may be the resulting material that can also have the ability to act as an anode material in LIB. Numerous metal oxide such as SnO_2 , Co_3O_4 , NiO , MnO_2 , Fe_3O_4 are used as an anode due to its high theoretical capacity and power density (Aras et al., 2022).

2.2.9 Iron oxides

Iron oxides are the materials that can act as an anode in lithium-ion batteries (LIB) due to their high theoretical storage capacity, low cost, and good safety. It was seen, the transition metal oxides have the potential to become anode material in LIB. Particularly two materials that are iron oxides (Fe_2O_3 , Fe_3O_4) because of their low cost, high corrosion resistance, and high theoretical capacity of iron oxides of approximately 1000 mAhg^{-1} (Behara et al., 2021; Cao et al., 1997).

Table -2.1 Portrays the cathode of Lithium ion batteries.

Material as cathode	Formula	Short Name	Abbreviation	Advantages	Ref
Lithium Cobalt oxide	LiCoO ₂	Li- Cobalt	LCO	Energy density is high.	(X. Zhang et al., 2021)
Lithium Manganese oxide	LiMn ₂ O ₄	Li- Manganese /spinel	LMO	Power density is high. Good safety.	(Persson et al., 2010)
Lithium iron phosphate	LiFePO ₄	Li- phosphate	LFP	Very safe. The cycling rate is high.	(Shi et al., 2016)
Lithium (M=Nickel Manganese Cobalt)oxide	LiNi _x Mn _y Co _z O ₂ (10-20% Co)	NMC	NMC	Very safe. Higher power density.	(Agosta et al., 2021)

Many advantages of iron oxides to working as an anode material as short negative ion (electron) diffusion length (path), high theoretical capacity. The advantage of using an iron-oxide-based anode can work for large-scale applications. It has plentiful electrochemical reactive sites. This material is eco-friendly. Iron oxides owing a good electrochemical performance (Raj et al., 2010). These elements are lightweight and low-cost. The lithium intercalation process of iron oxides is depend upon the redox reaction. Iron oxide (Fe₂O₃), the chemical reaction occurs (Aras et al., 2022).

Due to the low conductivity (2.2 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹), the charging and discharging of iron oxides also induce degradation. The high theoretical capacity and low conductivity are caused by volume expansion during the insertion of the process (Aras et al., 2022). Preparing the nanostructure material is a successful pathway toward the world of research on materials. The electrochemical process is raised into nano-structured based materials. So, a scientist researching this branch of science which is material science. Our main purpose is to find new materials to increase the life span and charging-discharging rate and remove main defects like degradation and dendrites.

Silicon is an element that has a theoretical higher capacity other materials than 4212 mAhg^{-1} (Li et al., 2021).

It has a large storage capacity to store lithium ions. But we have no practical use in industries because of its high volume expansion and low conductivity. Some papers reported a solution that makes composite material is an effective solution to decrease the volume expansion and increase the conductivity (Lu et al., 2022). We can also increase the conductivity by changing the electrochemical process. To confine the carbon nanoparticles into silicon. Now we started a study on iron oxides. These materials also have the same disadvantage as silicon. Iron oxides have a large theoretical capacity of 1000 mAhg^{-1} . These problems like low conductivity and high volume expansion during the intercalation of lithium ions (Li^+) in anode materials (Panda et al., 2022).

One paper reported a composite material that is graphene and iron oxide. This composite material provides a path to increase high theoretical capacity and cyclic capacity (Qin et al., 2003). Graphene, carbon nanotubes, and carbon nanoparticles are added to those materials to increase conductivity and stability. One solution is to fabricate (the process is done by different methods like photolithography, and laser machining) the nanoparticles, Nanorods, and nanotubes due to material iron oxide (Koster et al., 2012). The second solution is to make composite material such as combining carbon nanoparticles, Nanorods, and nanotubes with iron oxide. We determine here a simplistic way to prepare a nanocomposite from Quasi 1D graphene nanoribbons (GNRs) and iron oxide Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles (Yahia et al., 2012). The composite material increased the cell performance. For increasing the electrical conductivity and trying to decrease the volume expansion it is necessary to make composite material. Here composite material mean to combine material with iron oxides (Stoch et al., 2016). Mostly, we used graphite and carbon. Because it gives us a path for increasing electrical conductivity and stability of material. Three-dimensional structure of carbon is a best option for this process. Nano-based iron oxides based materials embedded into a three dimensional carbon structure (Ji et al., 2020). This composite material will enhance the electrical conductivity and lower the volume expansion. 3-D structures offers more storage and accessible sites for insertion of material (Hernández et al., 2022). This composite material is prepared by heating treatment (different processes). Theoretically, the storage capacity of this material after 300 cycles is 1220 mAhg^{-1} . But this composite material is not comfortable for widespread applications. Because this method of preparation of composite material requires high-cost (L. Zhang et al., 2021).

2.2.10 Transition metal Oxides

Transition metal oxides (TMOs) like FeO_x , SnO_2 , Co_3O_4 , NiO , and MnO_2 have high theoretical capacity. Due to their characteristics, they have the potential to act as an anode material (Jiao

et al., 2020). In applications, pulverization is produced because of volume expansion. This problem leads to eliminating the electrical contact. Researchers are trying to solve the problem of pulverization that is produced due to volume expansion. To prepare the nanostructure of iron oxide by fabrication method. Coating the carbon onto the iron oxides for electrical conductivity (Zhou et al., 2018). This is a prominent method to solve this problem. Because carbon and graphene play an important part to enhance their electrical conductivity and stability. Graphene helps all materials to increase their electrical conductivity and stability. Iron oxide (Fe_2O_3 , Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles incorporated with graphene matrices used as an anode in lithium-ion batteries have been reported (L. Zhang et al., 2021). Iron oxides (Fe_2O_3 , Fe_3O_4) and carbon nanotubes can be produced as composite material by using a method of hydro-thermal with chemical vapor deposition (CVD). Fundamentally, this is a better way to increase its electrical conductivity and make the material stable (Yang et al., 2020). The basic fault in this material is high volume expansion and low electrical conductivity. Researchers trying to solve these issues by using different methods. In this article, calculations are taken with the help of the XRD technique (Wang et al., 2016). The iron oxide is entrenched into the rGO (reduced graphene oxide) and makes a composite material and reduced ion graphene is prepared by the process of exfoliation of graphene to make graphene oxide. But after reading this article experimentally done through the Hummer method (Wang et al., 2009). To work as an anode in a lithium-ion battery, the composite material Fe_2O_3 / rGO electrode has starting discharge capacity of 1405mAhg^{-1} . After consecutive 250 cycles, It has a capacity of 812mAhg^{-1} . Fe_3O_4 / rGO composite nano-structured based material is combined with carbon by heat treatment. Carbon has the potential to tolerate mechanical stress, high conductivity, and low volume expansion. Due to these characteristics, researchers trying to make composite materials by using different processes like hydrothermal, CVD, impregnation, and electrospinning. This is an experimental paper (Liu et al., 2019). Firstly, prepared a composite material then analyzed of material by using the XRD technique, and then discussed the electrochemical process performed inside the battery (Jiao et al., 2020). All papers that have been reported on iron oxides as an anode material almost contain the same concept. In theoretical papers, the researcher used a different method to synthesize the material. The method that is used for the synthetic process of carbon nanostructure-based material or graphene. The nano-structure may be like nano-rods, nanoparticles (NPs), nanotubes, nano-flowers, nano-fabrics, and nano-sheets (Zhou et al., 2012).

2.3 Theoretical capacity without using DFT

One way is found to find the theoretical capacity of electrode materials (Klein et al., 2021).

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{host structure}}} \quad (2.2)$$

2.3.1 Cathode materials

We can easily find the theoretical capacity of cathode materials, because Cathode material contains lithium-atom (Jiao et al., 2020).

(i) Li-atom

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{Li}}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{1 * 26.8}{6.9}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 3880 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$$

(ii) LiFePO₄ (work as a cathode in LIBs)

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{LiFePO}_4}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{1 * 26.8}{158}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 170 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$$

(iii) LiCoO₂

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{LiCoO}_2}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{1 * 26.8}{97.87}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 273.83 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$$

(iv) LiMn₂O₄

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{LiMn}_2\text{O}_4}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{1 * 26.8}{180.8}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 148.2 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$$

2.3.2 Anode materials

In case of anode materials, 2D materials for LIBs can be usually divided into 5 categories (Aras et al., 2022).

- Graphene
- TMOs (transition metal oxides)
- TMDs (transition metal dichalcogenides)
- MXenes
- Xenes

(i) Graphene

(only carbon mass not Li)

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{C_6}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{1 * 26.8}{72}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 372.236 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$$

(ii) Li₂C₆ (Graphene)

(only carbon mass not Li)

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{C_6}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{2(1) * 26.8}{72}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 744.472 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$$

I. Transition metal oxides (TMOs)

The task is to find the theoretical capacity of anode material without using DFT. Firstly, we see a method to find the theoretical capacity of TMOs (transition metal oxides) as anode materials. The basic barrier is to find the theoretical capacity of anode material, which is "n." Through this equation, we are able to find the value of "n" (Zhang et al., 2020).

Where M= Fe, Co, Ni, Cu or Mn

(iii) Fe₂O

$$x = 2, y=3$$

n = no of lithium- atom

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{6 * 26.8}{159.69}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 1006.7\text{mAhg}^{-1}$$

(iv) Co₂O₄

$$x = 2, y=4$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{8 * 26.8}{181.86}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 1178.9 \text{mAhg}^{-1}$$

(v) Fe₃O₄

$$x = 3, y=4$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{8 * 26.8}{231.531}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 926.009 \text{mAhg}^{-1}$$

(vi) ZnO₃

$$x = 1, y=3$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{ZnO}_3}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{6 * 26.8}{113.377}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 1418.277 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$$

(vii) **Zn₂O₄**

$$x = 2, y = 4$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{Zn}_2\text{O}_4}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{8 * 26.8}{194.814}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 1100.57 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$$

(viii) **MnO₂**

$$x = 1, y = 2$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{MnO}_2}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{4 * 26.8}{86.9}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 1233.6 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$$

II. TMDs (Transition metal dichalcogenides)

Transition metal oxides with layered structure have high potential. The structure of transition metal oxides is MX_2 . Common 2D-TMDs are MoS_2 , VS_2 , VSe_2 , WS_2 . Where, $M = \text{Ti, W, V}$, and Mo $X = \text{Te, Se and S}$ Common 2D-TMDs are MoS_2 , VS_2 , VSe_2 , WS_2 . Through this equation we can find the value of “n” (Fu et al., 2021).

(ix) **MoS₂**

$$x = 1, y = 2$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{MoS}_2}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{4 * 26.8}{160}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 670\text{mAhg}^{-1}$$

(x) VSe₂

$$x = 1, y=2$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{VSe}_2}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{4 * 26.8}{208.861}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 513.26\text{mAhg}^{-1}$$

(xi) SnS₂

$$x = 1, y=2$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{SnS}_2}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{4 * 26.8}{182.81}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 586.326\text{mAhg}^{-1}$$

Some material values match perfectly with the reported paper values. Some values are close to the reported values of materials. I will mention the reference in the further report.

III. Transition metal carbonates (TMCs)

The reaction mechanism is

Where M= Co, Zn, and Fe (any transition metal), This equation for the transition metal carbonates (M-C-O), like CoCO_3 , MnCO_3 , and ZnCO_3 . (Dou & Fyta, 2020)

(xii) FeCO_3

x = 2

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{2 * F}{M_{\text{FeCO}_3}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{2 * 26.8}{115.842}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 462 \text{mAhg}^{-1}$$

(xiii) $\text{Fe}(\text{CO}_3)_2$

The equation can be written as

Li is more reactive metal than Fe. So, it replace with the Fe. Fe has oxidation state +4 in reactant side.

Reduction (Addition of electrons)

Oxidation (Removal of electrons)

x = 4

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{x * F}{M_{\text{Fe}(\text{CO}_3)_2}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{4 * 26.8}{175.86}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 609.59 \text{mAhg}^{-1}$$

In 2000, transition metal oxides (TMOs) were presented as an anode material in lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) and also introduced a conversion mechanism of reaction (Zhao et al., 2021). Due to this reaction, transition metal oxides decompose into $\text{M}^0/\text{Li}_2\text{O}$, and scientists estimate their theoretical capacities at 700 to 1000 mAhg^{-1} . But transition metal carbonates (TMCs)

decompose into M^0/Li_2CO_3 and estimate its theoretical capacity. We can find the theoretical capacity of any material if we are able to write down the general mechanism of a conversion reaction (Zhang et al., 2020).

(xiv) ABO₃ (SrRuO₃)

The following equation illustrates how SrRuO₃ undergoes oxidation and reduction (Ji et al., 2020).

Oxidation reaction

Reduction reaction

In this reaction, lithium ions (Li^+) and electrons (e^-) added to the compound SrRuO₃ to reduce it. Consequently, lithium oxide (Li_2O), ruthenium metal (Ru), and strontium ions (Sr^{2+}) produced (Behara et al., 2021). As SrRuO₃ goes through repeated cycles of oxidation and reduction during charge and discharge, these redox reactions are crucial to how the material functions as an anode in lithium-ion batteries. The effective operation of the battery made possible by the reversible redox processes that allow the storage and release of lithium ions within the anode (Ji et al., 2020).

To find the theoretical capacity of material is

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{SrRuO_3}} \quad (2.22)$$

The molecular weight of SrRuO₃ is 236.69 gmol⁻¹ and the calculated theoretical storage 670 mAhg⁻¹ is through balancing the redox reaction inside the guest atoms (x=6) and host.

2.4. Dependence of sites

The following are some variables that are dependent on sites.

2.4.1 Minimum Lithiation Energy

Lithium always intercalates on the site with the lowest energy that is best for the lithium atom. In 2D materials, the site detected is primarily the H site, and the minimum energy is always site dependent (Katz, 2020). Li intercalation in graphene and MOS₂ In the middle of the hexagonal ring, between the two layers of MOS₂/graphene, monolayers are discovered to be advantageous on the hollow H site. The structure has two intercalation sites: the octahedral and the tetrahedral. The octahedral site, where Li is coupled with four S atoms between the two layers, was shown

to be the most advantageous. Li, Na, and Mg have lithiation energies of -2.42, -0.44, and -0.87 eV, respectively. It has been discovered that the optimal site for Li intercalation is Oh octahedral, but no favorable site is computed for Na and Mg (Agosta et al., 2021).

2.4.2 Migration Path

Lithium ion battery rate performance is significantly influenced by the lithium transport/diffusion study. By obtaining many intermediate photos along a specific path, the computer analysis aids the diffusion rate conclusions. The diffusion path determines with the aid of the structure's accessible sites and then informs us of the optimal path for lithium in the host structure (Fei et al., 2021). All of the pathways in this investigation have energy differences of less than 350 MeV. Which way is best for visitor migration from one point to another is shown by the diffusion path. Diffusion of lamellar compounds has been seen to demonstrate that there is one path in the structure available in which there is no barrier for lithium where the O₂ release in the final phase (Yang et al., 2020). When calculating diffusion paths using DFT, several paths typically do not have the same energy barrier (Mitzi, 2019).

2.4.3 Electronic Band gap

The length of the interstitial channel affects the band gap variation and the shape of the wave function in various covalent conductors (Fei et al., 2021). The T-CrTe₂ bilayer stacking order determines the length of the interstitial channel; hence, the longer the interstitial channel, the more structural sites are available. Here, the link between two variables hexagonally and channel length is used to discuss the band gap. When a semiconductor material is lithiated, the introduction of lithium ions into the material can result in the electronic structure of the material changing from that of a semiconductor to that of a metal (Yang et al., 2020). This change in electronic structure can result in the material exhibiting metallic behavior, such as increased conductivity and decreased resistance. The extent of this change in electronic structure and the resulting behavior can depend on the specific material and the extent of lithiation. After performing the lithiation in the host material, the band gap is 0eV of the bilayer MoTe₂.

The bilayer Chromium dichloride (CrTe₂) is zero-bandgap material; it does not have a band gap in its electronic structure. Graphene (2D) also has no band gap (0eV) and commercially used electrode in lithium ion batteries. After lithiation, conductors typically do not change into another material (Ji et al., 2020). Lithiation refers to the process of introducing lithium ions into a material, and while this process can have an impact on the electronic structure and other properties of a material, it generally does not result in a change in the material itself (Hasan et al., 2022). However, the presence of lithium ions can affect the conductivity of a material, as

the movement of lithium ions through the material can result in changes to the distribution of charges and the overall conductivity of the material (Katz, 2020).

2.5. Perovskites Compounds

The mineral calcium titanium oxide (CaTiO_3), which was the first perovskite crystal to be found and is known as a perovskite compound (Katz, 2020). A Russian mineralogist Lev Perovski is honored by the name of the mineral, which was found in the Ural Mountains of Russia by Gustav Rose in 1839. Perovskites compounds has the general formula ABX_3 . A^{+2} and B^{+4} are positive metal cations, where A is usually alkaline earth metals i.e. Sr, Ca (s-block, Group-2A) and B is transition metals Fe, Ti, Ru (d-block). X^{-2} is an anion, where X is usually O and in rare case halogens F, Cl, Br and I (Fei et al., 2021). This displays the unit cell of ideal structure of perovskites (Hasan et al., 2022; Xu & Jiang, 2020).

Figure-2.9 The unit cell of perovskites compound (Turhan, 2012 #43).

We have eight octahedral in pink color that surrounded an A-atom and B-atom is present inside a octahedron which has only six coordinates (BX_6) with X-atoms. SrRuO_3 belongs to a widely known family ($\text{Sr}_{n+1}\text{Ru}_n\text{O}_{3n+1}$) of ruthenates and has an infinite layer of material ($n = \infty$) (Koster et al., 2012; Lin et al., 2021). In the perovskite compound SrRuO_3 , the Sr cation occupies the A site in the crystal structure, while the Ru cation occupies the B site (Gupta et al., 2015). The O anion occupies the X site, forming a BO_6 octahedron around the Ru cation. Since the Sr cation has a larger radius than the Ru cation, it requires a larger space to be accommodated in the crystal structure. This results in an expansion of the unit cell, which leads to the Sr cation occupying the interstitial sites in the crystal structure (Koster et al., 2012). Specifically, the Sr cation occupies the 12-coordinate face-centered cubic interstitial sites within the (001) planes of the perovskite structure. To visualize this, imagine the BO_6 octahedral formed by the Ru cations stacked on top of each other in a 3D lattice (Borges et al., 2010). The Sr cations then occupy the interstitial sites between these octahedral, forming a 3D network of corner-sharing BO_6 octahedral with Sr cations in the interstices. The resulting

crystal structure is known as a Ruddlesden-Popper phase, where the Sr cations are situated in the so-called "rock salt" layers, between the perovskite layers formed by the Ru-O octahedral. In the case of SrRuO₃, the formula is A₂B₂O₇, where A is Sr and B is Ru. This means that there are two perovskite layers in the structure (Borges et al., 2010). In the perovskite compound SrRuO₃, the Sr cation occupies the A site in the crystal structure, while the Ru cation occupies the B site (Gupta et al., 2015). The O anion occupies the X site, forming a BO₆ octahedron around the Ru cation. Since the Sr cation has a larger radius than the Ru cation, it requires a larger space to be accommodated in the crystal structure.

Figure 2.10 Structure of SrRuO₃ (Borges et al., 2010).

The crystal structure of SrRuO₃ is called a Ruddlesden-Popper phase because it belongs to a family of compounds known as Ruddlesden-Popper oxides. The Ruddlesden-Popper phases are a class of layered perovskite oxides that have the general formula A_{n+1}B_nO_{3n+1} (Katz, 2020). In this formula, A represents a large cation, B represents a smaller transition metal cation, and n is an integer that determines the number of perovskite layers in the structure (Chakrabarti et al., 2003).

2.5.1 Multivalent ion batteries (Not included LIBs)

In multivalent ion batteries group, lithium ion battery does not involved. Lithium ions are not engaged in the charge-discharge process in multivalent ion batteries, such as magnesium or calcium ion batteries (Gupta et al., 2015). Since these batteries employ ions with several positive charges (multivalent ions Mg²⁺ or Ca²⁺) as the charge carriers rather than lithium ions with a single positive charge (Aras et al., 2022).

2.5.2 Magnesium ion batteries (Mg²⁺)

Due to the increased charge density of the magnesium (Mg²⁺) ion used in these batteries, they may be able to provide greater energy densities than lithium-ion batteries. For uses including grid-scale energy storage and electric cars and magnesium-ion batteries are being researched (Agosta et al., 2021).

2.5.3 Calcium ion batteries (Ca^{2+})

The charge carrier in these batteries is calcium (Ca^{2+}) ions, which also have a higher charge density than lithium ions. Compared to lithium-ion batteries, calcium-ion batteries have the potential to provide greater energy density and increased safety. For calcium-ion batteries, research is still being done to develop suitable electrode materials and electrolytes (Grinberg et al., 2004).

2.5.4 Zinc ion batteries (Zn^{2+})

These batteries employ zinc (Zn^{2+}) ions, which are more accessible and less costly than lithium, as the charge carrier. Applications for zinc-ion batteries include grid-scale energy storage (Li et al., 2018).

2.5.5 Al ion batteries (Al^{3+})

Aluminum (Al^{3+}) ions, which are plentiful and have a high charge density that used as the charge carrier in these batteries. Aluminum-ion batteries being researched for uses like stationary energy storage and electric cars because they have high energy density and cheap cost (Ma et al., 2022).

2.5.6 SrRuO_3 used as cathode in multivalent ion batteries

For multivalent ion batteries, the perovskite oxide material SrRuO_3 investigated as a possible cathode material. Instead of the conventional Li^{2+} ion in lithium-ion batteries, these batteries employ ions with multiple positive charges such as Mg^{2+} or Ca^{2+} as the charge carriers (Liu et al., 2019). The function of this material SrRuO_3 in this scenario would be to help in the transfer of charge between the cathode and the multivalent ions in the electrolyte. In particular, it serves as a catalyst to speed up the conversion process of multivalent ions batteries with the cathode material (Ma et al., 2022). The study is also investigate the structural and morphological characteristics of SrRuO_3 in order to comprehend how well it functions as a cathode material. The electrochemical characteristics and endurance depends on its crystal structure and particle size of material SrRuO_3 (Lin et al., 2021).

2.5.7 Role of TEM

The microstructure and chemical composition of material examined at the nanoscale with the use of TEM (Agosta et al., 2021). Understanding the changes in structure and degradation mechanisms that take place during battery cycling in the framework of multivalent ion battery cathodes has an impact on the development of innovative electrode materials with improved performance and stability. SrRuO_3 was show to have strong electrochemical properties for use as a cathode material in magnesium-ion batteries, showing consistent cycling performance and high energy density (Yang, 2021).

2.5.8 Thin films SrRuO₃

The article describes a study of Mg intercalation in single-crystal thin-film Mn₂O₄ host structures at atomic resolution (Sun et al., 2018). In the work, Li ions de-intercalated after forming thin LiMn₂O₄ films on SrTiO₃ using pulsed laser deposition. The electrochemistry of Mg ions intercalation then carried out in a specially built X-ray transmission cell using Mn₂O₄ as the host cathode structure, Mg as the anode and the necessary electrolyte. The plus point of SrRuO₃ kept its conductivity and crystallinity over the cycling voltage range of 2.0-4.3V (Purbawati et al., 2020). According to author of this paper, Li-ion batteries (LIBs) are currently the backbone of rechargeable batteries. The monovalency of Li¹⁺ ions means that LIBs have a naturally constrained capacity (Meng et al., 2021). Lithium has an atomic size of around 152 Pico meters (pm), while magnesium has an atomic size of roughly 160 pm. This indicates that lithium ions are somewhat smaller than magnesium ions; however, the size difference is negligible (X. Zhang et al., 2021). Mg ion batteries are a very appealing alternative for reaching high energy density because Mg²⁺ ions although being similar in size to Li⁺ ions have the capacity to hold twice as much charge after intercalation. Nevertheless, finding a good electrolyte and cathode structure combination is necessary to overcome the difficulty of Mg intercalation into the host material. The fabrication process and electrochemical properties of multi-layer epitaxial thin film electrodes constructed of LiMn₂O₄ and SrRuO₃ covered in the article (Purbawati et al., 2020). The work will employ pulsed laser deposition to make the thin film electrodes on SrTiO₃ substrates. The author examines at the crystal structure and morphology of the electrodes using SEM and X-ray diffraction (Yang et al., 2023). The electrochemical properties of the electrodes are further investigate using cyclic voltammetry and charge-discharge experiments. According to the study, LiMn₂O₄ and SrRuO₃ multi-layer epitaxial thin film electrodes have outstanding electrochemical properties, such as high capacity and great cycle stability (Liu et al., 2022). These multi-layer epitaxial thin film electrodes might be useful in commercial lithium-ion batteries with great performance. A SrRuO₃ buffer layer is a thin layer of strontium ruthenium oxide that employed as a conductive and crystalline buffer layer between the substrate and the electrode material such as LiMn₂O₄ or LiNi_{0.5}Mn_{1.5}O₄ during the manufacture of thin-film electrodes (Grinberg et al., 2004). The electrode performs better overall because contribution of the buffer layers to the electrical and structural characteristics of the electrode material (Koster et al., 2012). The main and foremost task requirement to choose that anode and cathode which has high conductivity. This material would prove perfect for both cathode as well as anode in rechargeable ion batteries. As a conductive buffer layer of SrRuO₃ used between the substrate and the LiCoO₂ film (Grinberg et al., 2004). The epitaxial development of the LiCoO₂ film, which is vital for preserving the crystal structure and enhancing the performance of the electrode material made possible by the SrRuO₃ of buffer layer. Further boosting the electrochemical performance of the resultant LiCoO₂/SrRuO₃

composite electrode, SrRuO₃ also acted as a conductive layer that made it easier for electrons to move between the substrate and the LiCoO₂ film (Liu et al., 2019). The work will employ pulsed laser deposition to make the thin film electrodes on SrTiO₃ substrates. The author examines at the crystal structure and morphology of the electrodes using SEM and X-ray diffraction (Yang et al., 2023). The electrochemical properties of the electrodes are further investigate using cyclic voltammetry and charge-discharge experiments. Certain anode materials exhibit high theoretical capacity, as shown in the table below. However, two main issues often plague these materials: volume expansion and low conductivity (Li et al., 2021).

Table-2.2 This displayed an anode material, theoretical capacities, ionic conductivity, typically initial columbic efficiency and volume change.

Anode Materials	Graphite	Silicon (Si)	SiO ₂
Theoretical Capacity (mAhg ⁻¹)	330 - 430	4200	1965
Ionic Conductivity (Scm ⁻¹)	10 ⁵	10 ⁻¹	>10 ⁻¹
Typical initial columbic efficiency (%)	90 – 95	70 – 85	52.38
Volume change (%)	10	300	100
Ref	(Nitta et al., 2015; Zhu et al., 2019)	(Jiao et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2019)	(Jiao et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2016; Zhou et al., 2018)

Graphite is a widely used commercial anode material due to its high ionic conductivity, although it has a relatively low theoretical capacity when compared to materials such as silicon and silicon dioxide. The high diffusion coefficient of graphite results in better conductivity and lower volume and lattice constant expansion, thus making it an attractive choice for anode applications (Liu et al., 2022). The perovskite compound SrRuO₃ is the combination of three elements that are Sr, Ru and O. The primary active element in SrRuO₃ is ruthenium (Ru). A highly conductive metal works well as a catalyst in SOFCs (solid oxide fuel cells) for the electrochemical oxidation of fuels like hydrogen. Ru is appropriate for use in SOFC anodes because of its strong stability at high temperatures and in the presence of reducing gases. SrRuO₃ is dope with strontium (Sr) to increase its electrical conductivity and stability (Koster et al., 2012). In the perovskite structure, Sr replaces element of the Ca or Ba atoms resulting in oxygen vacancies and encouraging the development of conductive channels. At high temperatures, Sr also helps in maintaining the SrRuO₃ crystal structure not leading to structure deformation. As it contributes to the redox reactions that take place during the oxidation of material and forms the perovskite crystal structure, oxygen (O) is a crucial component of SrRuO₃ (Hasan et al., 2022). The important factor is that oxygen (3.44) is second highest

electronegative element after fluorine (3.98). Due to high electronegativity, it has more power as a component of anode material to get more valance electrons from the guest atom such as lithium, magnesium and calcium (Aras et al., 2022).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The following parts provide a theoretical backdrop for the study, a description of the ideas and theories involved, the tactics used, and computational details (Borges et al., 2010).

3.1 Theoretical Framework

Here, the theoretical foundation for the DFT-based calculations employed in this thesis is given. It just includes the portion of my work based on that specific computational theory, not the entire theory of the DFT. DOS (Density of States), band structures, and structural properties (bond length, bond angle, etc.) are among the discoveries made in this effort (Eriksson et al., 1994).

3.1.1 Schrödinger equation of motion

The Schrödinger equation, which employs the partial differential equation, can be used to determine the electronic wave function. With the use of energy conservation, we may determine various atom properties using this equation. The Schrödinger equation, which the DFT-based computational theory implements, can be used to analyse the characteristics of batteries (Khan et al., 2021). We can discover an electron's characteristics, such as its electronic band structure, particle size, quantum numbers, effective mass, and state density, among others. It is possible to write the Schrödinger equation in its most basic form, which is significant for non-relativistic effects, as (Stoch et al., 2016).

$$\mathcal{H}\psi = E\psi \quad (3.1)$$

The wave function of that one electron or many electrons in the system is represented by the letter ψ in this equation, which is the Hamiltonian operator that governs the motion of the nuclei and electrons (Stoch et al., 2016). The system's nuclei are indicated by a capital R , and its electrons are indicated by a minuscule r in these brackets. The eigenvalue E on the right side is dependent on the ground state density of the system given the least energy in the system (Nitta et al., 2015).

$$\mathcal{H} = T_e + T_n + V_{ee} + V_{nn} - V_{en} \quad (3.2)$$

Here, we can see that the Hamiltonian has five terms: the first term is the electrons' kinetic energy, T_e ; the second term is the nuclei's kinetic energy; the third term is the system's repellent interactions between electrons; the fourth term is the repellent interactions between any two nuclei present in the system; and the final term is the system's attractive interactions between electrons (Borges et al., 2010).

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + V(r) \right] \psi = E\psi \quad (3.3)$$

The Planck's constant in this equation is equal to $\frac{h}{2\pi} = 6.64 \times 10^{-34}$ Js , M is mass of electron 9.1×10^{-31} . The operator is differential is ∇^2 ,the potential energy is represented by the final term, $V(r)$ (Orio et al., 2009). Most materials studied computationally have more than one electron, which transforms the problem into the many-body problem. To solve this, DFT calculates the S.E. with degrees of freedom $3m+3n$, and in this system, every interaction must be evaluated with one electron to any other electron, with one electron to nuclei, or with nuclei to another nucleus. In this case, it is necessary to take into account every interaction that exists in the system (Cohen et al., 2012). There are numerous assumptions required to solve the Schrödinger equation for many body systems because this equation can only be precisely obtained for hydrogen atoms with one electron, and the system grows complex with more electrons (Burke, 2012). When a system only has one electron, such a hydrogen atom, the wave equation can be solved equation, however when the system's electron count increases, it becomes impossible to utilize this equation for systems with more than one electron. In order to address the myriad bodily issues, approximations are used, and the results we obtain are not precise but rather (Goodenough & Park, 2013). The Born Oppenheimer approximation is the first approximation, and it holds that the motion of electrons and nuclei should be handled independently (Grinberg et al., 2004). This theorem divides the electronic and nuclei portions of the electronic wave equation into two pieces. There are numerous assumptions required to solve the Schrödinger equation for many body systems because this equation can only be precisely obtained for hydrogen atoms with one electron, and the system grows complex with more electrons. In this case, it is necessary to take into account every interaction that exists in the system (Tada et al., 2019).

3.1.2 Born-Oppenheimer Hamiltonian

Consider the following Hamiltonian for a molecule . In this approximation, the wave function of any system will divide into two pieces (Tada et al., 2019).

$$\mathcal{H}\psi_i (r_i, R_I) = \psi_e(r_i, R_I)\psi_n(R_I) \quad (3.4)$$

The electronic wave function is the first term on the right side of the equation above, and the nuclear wave function is the second term. The nucleus's coordinates are treated as static in this approach, whereas only the electronic coordinates are considered to be in motion. Using this approximate method, the total energy becomes (Orio et al., 2009).

$$E_{\text{total}} = E_e + E_n \quad (3.5)$$

The $3m+3n$ degrees of freedom that were previously employed are reduced to merely $3n$ coordinates in this approximation method, making the S.E. simpler and easier to solve. In the scenario where the nuclei are larger than the electrons, there is extremely little likelihood of inaccuracy in the atoms using this approximation (Grinberg et al., 2004).

$$H = T_e + T_n + U(r, Q) \quad (3.5)$$

$$\Psi_{\text{total}} = \Psi_{\text{electronic}} \times \Psi_{\text{nuclei}} \quad (3.6)$$

In this equation, T_e and T_n are the kinetic energies of electron and nuclei and $U(r, Q)$ is the potential term (Ma et al., 2022). The terms r and Q in this phrase stand for the electronic coordinates and the nucleus coordinates, respectively. When T_n is fixed in equation, the motion of the nuclei is not taken into account, making the equation simpler than it was before this approximation. Additionally, the following definitions apply to orthonormal wave function and energies (Grinberg et al., 2004).

$$[H_e - V_n(Q)] = \phi_n(r, Q) \quad (3.7)$$

$$H_e = T_e + U(r, Q) \quad (3.8)$$

It here reflects the Born Oppenheimer Approximation's electronic states and potential energy surfaces (Nitta et al., 2015). The electrical, vibrational, and rotational energies all have a relationship with one another in energies. Many physicists recommend alternative approximations after this one, such as Hartree Fock with additional limitations in the system of many body Hamiltonian. After introducing the Born Oppenheimer Approximation technique, ab initio and DFT-based theories are introduced. The wave function served as the foundation for the HF approach, which can be used to determine the minimum energy (Li et al., 2021). However, after the discovery of DFT, this wave function method was replaced by the electron density in the system, which can be used to determine the energy.

3.1.3 Hartree–Fock (HF) method

Due to the inclusion of the electronic structural theory's descriptive nature, the HF model is described. This approach asserts that all electronic motion may be found by understanding the single electron orbital, which is related to electronic motion. It is not necessary to be aware of the motion of every particle in the system (Chen et al., 2020). The Schrödinger equation can be simply solved for the lone electron present in the hydrogen atom to determine the system's minimal energy. However, the HF technique, which ignores the electron-electron repulsive interactions, can be used to compute the Hamiltonian for systems with more than one electron (Shimizu et al., 2021). The wave function would then change to $V_{ee} = 0$:

$$\psi (r_1, r_2) = \psi_H (r_1) \psi_H (r_2) \quad (3.9)$$

We assumed in the procedure that the electrons are independent of one another and that the impact of one atom has no bearing on the other electron. Following the HF technique, the wave function can be expressed as (Tuca et al., 2022).

$$\psi_{HP} (r_1, r_2, \dots, r_N) = \phi_1(r_1)\phi_2(r_2) \dots \phi_N(r_N) \quad (3.10)$$

The Hartree Fock product of linear combination of atomic orbitals is the result of the linear combination of atomic orbitals. The flaw with this is that it did not satisfy the conditions of the antisymmetric principle (Prasad et al., 2022).

3.1.4 Slater Determinant

The Slater determinant that the wave function can be expressed as can resolve the antisymmetric principle issue (Wieduwilt et al., 2020).

$$\psi (x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}[\chi_1(x_1)\chi_2(x_2) - \chi_1(x_2)\chi_2(x_1)] \quad (3.11)$$

Now that the antisymmetric principle is satisfied, using the Slater determinant with the post-HF approach for the correlational energy term does not cause any issues for the HF method. However, the aforementioned equation may be used to cases with two electrons. For instance, if one electron is added to a hydrogen atom, the system now has two electronic components, and it can be solved using the method described above.

what might occur if there were more than two electrons, the two electrical equations mentioned above would then become (Barca et al., 2020).

$$\psi (x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{vmatrix} \chi_1(x_1) & \chi_2(x_1) \\ \chi_1(x_2) & \chi_2(x_2) \end{vmatrix} \quad (3.12)$$

It should be noted that the preceding equation yields 0 if one places two electrons in an orbital that is the same for two electrons and this procedure occurs at the same moment. Therefore, we will receive (Burke, 2012; Wieduwilt et al., 2020).

$$\psi (x_1, x_2) = 0 \quad (3.13)$$

And for N electronic systems, the Slater determinant will be

$$\psi = \frac{1}{N} \begin{vmatrix} \chi_1(x_1) & \chi_2(x_1) & \chi_3(x_1) \\ \chi_1(x_1) & \chi_2(x_1) & \chi_3(x_1) \\ \chi_1(x_1) & \chi_2(x_1) & \chi_3(x_1) \end{vmatrix} \quad (3.14)$$

The electrical system with more than two electrons uses this as the Slater determinant of the spin orbitals. According to some strong quantum mechanics laws, in this system it is impossible to discriminate between any of the electrons. Every electron in the system is capable of

occupying every electronic orbital. In order to find the least energy solution, it is necessary to build the Slater determinant (Raj et al., 2010). The HF technique was first introduced by D.R. Hartree in 1928, and Fock enhanced it further in 1930. This approximation method reduces the electronic system's entire wave function to a single electron wave function, making it simpler than it was in the electronic case before the reduction (Khan et al., 2021). Later, with the understanding that the sum of the basic functions is included in this approximation, this method was simplified and made useful. Additionally, utilizing this approximation and the available iterations in the system, the S.E. can be solved for a variety of body systems (Khan et al., 2021). By employing an iterative technique, the spin orbitals are here solved using the Hamiltonian of the relevant system in order to determine the system's minimal energy. Using the potential of the system and the Pauli exclusion principle, it is possible to precisely compute the exchange energy in this interaction. However, in this case, the correlational portion of the energy, the second component of the XC functional, is completely disregarded. However, the outcomes of the overstated energy in the total energy computation are provided by this approximation. However, the post-HF approach created by Moller-Plesset employing configuration interaction can incorporate this term energy (Stoch et al., 2016).

3.2 DFT (density functional theory)

Even with the BOA, the system still has four degrees of freedom: three for the electrons' spatial coordinates and one for their spin coordinates. The two theorems presented by scientists Kohn and Hohenberg serve as the foundation for the entire theory included in the DFT. The very first version of the theorem, developed by Kohn and Hohenberg, contains the following assertion (Borges et al., 2010).

“The Schrödinger equation's ground state energy is used in the functional for electronic density.”

This theorem should make it obvious that there is a connection between the electrons' ground state energy and their density. As approximations, many functionals are used. One might infer from the functionalism name that it has something in common with functions. Here, a mathematical function example is provided to help explain the ideas at play (Eriksson et al., 1994).

$$f(x) = x^2 + 1 \quad (3.15)$$

Functionals and functions are quite similar, however a functional requires a single integer, which is then used to get the functional value. According to this approximation, it was claimed that one could find practically all of the material's electrical properties by using ground state energy (Shi et al., 2016). This theorem implies that all spatial degrees of freedom may be found simply

determining the electronic density, allowing us to quickly determine the ground state energy and other relevant properties of our material by DFT calculations. This theorem informs us that physical qualities can be readily discovered using DFT theory and the electronic density, however it is ambiguous regarding the functional (Yahia et al., 2012).

3.2.1 Fermi Model

This technique was developed by Thomas and Fermi using the electrons' spatial and spin coordinates as a product. The three-dimensional coordinates of the spatial coordinates are x, y, and z. It is possible to express the integration over the electronic density as (Hussain et al., 2020).

$$\int \rho(r) dr = n \quad (3.16)$$

By assuming that the system's electron density is constant, it is possible to determine the electronic energy. The computations are carried out using the conventional management of several body systems. In this model, the exchange and correlation energy factors are not taken into account. In 1930, Dirac added a new term to this model for the study of the exchange energy term in an effort to improve it (Liao et al., 2022). According to this concept, the electronic density should be used instead of the electronic wave function in the Schrödinger equation to determine the many-body system's ground state energy (Sofi & Gupta, 2020). Only the infinite charge model was supported by this model, not the finite charge model. By using this novel approach and making certain adjustments to the original equation, the Schrödinger equation can be solved (Yang, 2021).

$$t(r) = \int \frac{p^2}{2m_e} n(r) F_{rp} dp \quad (3.17)$$

And

$$t(r) = C_{kin} [n(r)]^{5/3} \quad (3.18)$$

The kinetic energy term is an approximation that is not precisely defined, and this technique does not include the exchange energy part because of the theory of Pauli exclusion principle (Borges et al., 2010). Although this model is an improvement in S.E. and a significant step from earlier theory, it still has several flaws. Dirac added the exchange energy term in 1928 (Stoch et al., 2016). This model's lack of accuracy is caused by the term mistakes in the kinetic energy term and full neglect of the term correlation in this case. Later, Ewald Teller demonstrated that due to the differential energies of the individual and sums of the bonding atoms energies, the energy computed from the TF model is not accurate for expressing the exact energy of linked atoms. When the system's bond length increases, the total energy is calculated incorrectly as a result of this inaccuracy (Adamescu et al., 2014).

3.2.2 Hohenberg-Kohn-Mermin Theorem HK2

Two main points of this theorem:

When external potential is present, the ground state density can be used to determine how uniquely functional the external potential is. For this system, the Hamiltonian can be expressed (LeMaitre, 2022).

$$H = T + V_{ee} + V_{ext} \quad (3.19)$$

The Hamiltonian, wave function and total energy are all related in this claim, and their relationship can be expressed as (Nie et al., 2023).

$$\rho = V_{ext} = H = \psi = E \quad (3.20)$$

The energy of that actual ground state density must be equal to in these equations for the system's total energy to be equal to that density's energy $E_\rho \geq E_{\rho_0}$. The second theorem argues that if one can determine the correct electronic density of the ground states, that density truly indicates the atomic states' ground state energy. To attain the minimized energy states, we can change the ground state density up until we reach the minimal energy (Nitta et al., 2015). The variation approach can be used to adjust the electronic density until the minimal energy is obtained for this approximation that we use to get the genuine ground state density. The functional can be expressed using the form below (Zhu et al., 2019). The Kohn Sham approach will be used as the next technique to define the functional value that is still explicitly unknown. The functional is split into two sections. The wave function's straightforward analytical expression appears in the first section, whereas all other parts appear in the second. The first term has four additional components, including electron-electron repulsions, electron-nuclei interactions, and electron-nuclei interactions (Shimizu et al., 2021). The exchange correlational term, or E_{XC} phrase, is used to describe all other terms that are unknown. All of the system's quantum mechanical effects fall under this umbrella term. The Kohn Sham equation can be stated as the answer to three spatially coordinated equations, and as a result, there are three terms in the equation above that are added together using an XC functional. On the left side of the equation, there are three potentials that are similar to the three spatial coordinates mentioned before (Zhou et al., 2022). The V , V_h , and V_{xc} are the three potentials. The first potential is the same as how the Schrodinger equation is described, the second potential is the Hartree potential, which is denoted by the letter h, and the exchange correlational potential is denoted by the last potential (Zhao et al., 2021). First, we must determine the electrical density, and in order to do so, we must determine the single electron wave function. In order to determine the true electrical density, this theorem uses the following iterative steps:

3.3 Theorems associate Kohn Sham equation

In some Kohn-Sham equations-related theorems, the system is subjected to an external potential in order to assess differences, and this external potential disturbs the system's electrons (Adam et al., 2019).

3.3.1 Theorem 1

The external applied potential in the system of interest can be used to determine the electronic density. Let's assume there are two external potentials $V(r)$ and $V'(r)$ that share identical external potential. Here, the wave functions are different despite the similar ground state densities for two different Hamiltonians. The following expression can be constructed using the variation principle (Annamalai, 2022).

$$E_0 \langle \psi' | H | \psi' \rangle = \langle \psi' | H' | \psi' \rangle + \langle \psi' | H - H' | \psi' \rangle \quad (3.21)$$

3.3.2 Theorem 2

The exact minimum total energy is provided by the ground state density. Consider a trial density in this case $\rho'(r)$. Using this density, we can first determine the wave function from that test density, and then we can build the Hamiltonian (Masoud & Stone, 2019).

$$H \langle \psi' | H' | \psi' \rangle = E[\rho'] \geq E_0[\rho_0] \quad (3.22)$$

The kinetic energy functionals, electron functionals, and nucleus electron functionals are all included in this theorem. By using this theorem, one may determine the minimal energy term.

3.4. Kohn Sham Equation

According to this method, the system that may be used for computations is a non-interacting electronic system, and the ground state density is taken into account while doing calculations. For simpler computations, the kinetic energy quantity is further split into two components. There are two types of kinetic energies: one is the kinetic energy of a system that is not interacting, and the other is that of a system that is. The distinction can be expressed as follows (Masoud & Stone, 2019).

$$\Delta T = T_0 - T_s \quad (3.23)$$

Then the F_{HK} the unknown factor can be written as

$$F_{HK} = T_s + J(\rho) + (T_0 - T_s) + E_{nuc}(\rho) \quad (3.24)$$

The core term in the equation above is in the exchange energy term, while the very right side of the equation is in the E_{xc} functional. Additionally, this function takes into account the variations in kinetic energy between the two various systems, such as interacting and noninteracting particles. The fictional system is another name for the interactive system in

which all atoms are interacting, and the DFT calculations would take that interaction into account. E_{XC} is still not entirely understood (Borges et al., 2010).

3.4.1 XC Functional

Following is a description of popular functionals (Kato & Saito, 2022) :

3.4.2 LDA (Local density approximation)

Every electrical system is approximated here as a localised, uniform electron gas. The most popular and computationally affordable model is known as LDA. In this case, the system that is contributing is the noninteracting system, where the positive charges are dispersed over the entire system and the electrons move randomly and interact with one another. The charges in this system are not simply positive or negative; they are also regarded as neutral in the electronic many-body system. It is possible to write this XC functional using the LDA technique as:

$$E_{LDA}(\rho) = \int \rho(r) e_{xc}(\rho)r dr \quad (3.25)$$

The energy of the exchange correlational per electron of the system is represented by the term e_{xc} on the right side of the equation above, and the location with density is represented by the term r . The product of the two components presented below may be used to represent the second term on the right side of the equation above:

$$\varepsilon_{XC} = \varepsilon_x + \varepsilon_c \quad (3.26)$$

The energy of the exchange functional and the energy of the correlational functional are the two terms products specified in the equation above. This method's upgraded version uses a new theoretical equation and incorporates the spin component into the local density approximation, which is therefore referred to as the LSDA (Local Spin Density Approximation).

This approximation is more suited for uncontrolled systems than the standard LDA since it appropriately assigns the spins of spin up and spin down electrons. This approximation is typically taken into account for system interactions that occur across small distances.

3.4.3 Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA-PBE)

By include the gradient of the system's density, this technique differs significantly from the preceding one. The. In order to accurately describe the XC functional of the GGA in the calculation of the energy, one must use additional approximations, such as the PW91 approximation method, the P86 approximation method, or the PBE approximation method created by Perdew Burke Erenzerh. The PBE functional with GGA was employed in this thesis, and the XC term for PBE is presented below:

$$E_{XC(PBE)} = \int \rho(r) \epsilon_x F_x dr \quad (3.27)$$

In contrast to the straightforward theory of LDA, the PBE energy component is less straightforward and uses more complex formulae. Results from the GGA with PBE extension will be more precise than those from the LDA when it comes to things like total energy calculations and lattice constants. The GGA(PBE) is the most popular XC functional in DFT computations, particularly for battery applications. Another benefit is that it provides correct findings for system long-range interactions.

3.4.4 Vander Waals Interaction (vdWs)

Different functionals are accessible in the DFT theory for Vander Waals interactions and the dispersion correction. In the systems without bonds, these are the weak interactions between the atoms that are depicted. According to functional requirements that characterise the dispersion factor in the system, including Vander Waals or weak contacts, these explain many of the features of the materials. The Vander Waals effect plays a crucial role between the two-dimensional layers of graphite or any other two-dimensional material.

The DFT theory has a fundamental problem in that it treats the dispersion and Vander Waals relations in dipoles as weak interactions. The study of the Vander Waals interactions is necessary for layer structure investigations, therefore additional dispersion corrections, such as the D3 correction by Becke Jonson and the VDWDF Vander Waals density functional, are introduced to the system.

3.4.5 Orbital basis functions

The product of the combination of the orbital basis functions is used to derive the minimal energy of the system in order to solve the Kohn-Sham equation. In fact, the Kohn Sham equation is adequately described using the basis functions.

3.5. Computational Details

The ADF-BAND package, based on the Kohn Sham method to density functional theory, is used for all computations in this thesis. In this case, the SCF approach is based on the Direct Inversion of Iterative Subspace method (DIIS), which employed a highly optimised numerical integration strategy for the Hamiltonian evaluation. When energy and force requirements are smaller than 0.00027eV and 0.027eV/, respectively, atomic locations should converge. The sole method used to determine the site energies is single point (SP) computations, which compute the nuclear gradients and hessian derivatives on a single point throughout the course of seven simulations.

3.5.1 Frozen Approximation

Although the computation time is sped up by using the frozen core approximation, the system still contains electrons that differ by pseudopotential. In these computations, the inner atomic shells are merely frozen.

3.5.2 XC Functional

The XC functional utilised in this implementation is the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange component of PBE, which was implemented by the GGA.

3.5.3 Numerical Quality

The numerical quality reflects how well the fuzzy cell strategy created by used numerical integration. The fuzzy cells are areas where overlapping atomic centre regions coexist. These spaces are therefore seen as integrated spherical grid centres.

3.5.4 Basis Set

The linear arrangement of basis functions or basis sets used in BAND to describe the electrical wave function. Due to the more precise behaviour of STOs close to the nucleus, this code provides localised basis functions using Slater Type Orbitals or Numerical Type Orbitals (NTOs), but not Gaussian Type Orbitals. The Triple Zeta Plus Polarisation basis set, which maintains the optimal balance between accuracy and performance, was employed in these computations.

3.5.5 DOS and Band Structure Calculation

The host structure is next optimised using a 2x2 supercell according to the same standards as before. The standard route in the Brillouin zone along K, via which the DOS and band structures are computed, was automatically constructed in the BAND code. With the exception of site calculations, all calculations are carried out by totally relaxing the structure. In every computation, there are no restrictions placed on any atom. By default, BAND uses the Hirschfeld analysis to determine the charges of the well-localized bound atoms. The bulk CrTe₂ predicted band gap of 0eV is comparably satisfactory for both experimental and theoretical findings.

3.5.6 DFTB

Next, calculations are carried out using DFTB, which stands for density functional based tight binding technique for molecules and periodic systems. This approach is used to study the

lithium migration barrier and structural stability of the host structure. In compared to BAND, this quick approximation approach saves a lot of computing time.

3.5.7 CI-NEB

The enhanced NEB method known as (CI-NEB) climbing image nudged elastic band is used to determine the path of lithium's. Every path optimises 3 numbers of photos, excluding the numbers of the beginning and end images. These pictures are not independent of one another, rather each image's forces are reliant on those of its closest neighbour. Parallel forces are removed throughout the reaction route, and spring forces are supplied to retain the middle pictures in the centre of the diffusion curve. They were able to prevent the centre pictures from overlapping on the first or last image thanks to this. Local optimisation, which optimises each picture independently, is the optimisation technique used for CI-NEB in these computations.

3.5.8 Molecular dynamics (MD)

Equation numerical integration is used to carry out Molecular Dynamic simulation. The motion that is applied to replicate a system's temporal development. Because they are independent of computer time and are employed in MD computations, 1fs time steps errors. There are 500 steps taken in total. Because these variables are useless for 3D systems, angular momentum and centre of mass are disregarded. Temperature readings between 100 and 500 K are used to assess the impact on the structure. The next step is to evaluate the material attributes as a battery after identifying all these features.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the structural properties, electronic properties, theoretical storage capacity, migration/diffusion path of host materials MoTe₂ and CrTe₂ through NEB thoroughly analyzed. The extracted results and the resulting interpretations presented in comparison study of both the materials. Before discussing Li insertion in bilayer CrTe₂ and MoTe₂, we first examined the electronic and structural properties of both host materials. Specifically, the electronic properties of materials analysis highlights how the adsorption of Li changes the electronic properties to a metallic state, which is beneficial for electron conductivity in anode materials. The structural and electrical properties of host materials before and after the insertion of lithium atoms have discussed below.

4.1 Structural properties

The atomic structures of the CrTe₂ bilayer and MoTe₂ are shown in Figures a,c. From the top view, the bilayer CrTe₂ and MoTe₂ sheets possess a standard trigonal and hexagonal structure with the space group $P\bar{3}m1$ and $P6_3/mmc$ symmetry. From the side view, the MoTe₂ and CrTe₂ bilayer sheet has a three-atomic-layer structure with one Cr and Mo sublayer sandwiched with two Te sublayers, and each Mo and Cr atom is surrounded by two Te atoms (Te-Cr/Mo-Te) due to the chemical ratio of M: X being 1:2, they form an X-M-X covalently connected hexagonal quasi-2D lattice in figures b and d, The structure of supercell (4x4) of bilayer CrTe₂ as a host material is composed of 96 atoms, made up of 32 chromium and 64 tellurium atoms. The convergence of these atoms resulted in the formation of three layers with an interlayer distance of 3.28 Å. Supercell (4x4) of bilayer MoTe₂ as a host material consists of 101 atoms, including 32 molybdenum and 64 tellurium atoms. These convergence of atom led to the development of bilayer with an interlayer spacing of 3.11 Å. Bilayer CrTe₂ 3.00 Å has a twofold shorter interlayer distance than MoTe₂. The lithiation of in bilayer or layered host materials does not depend upon the interlayer distance. The 1T phase contains Te-Cr-Te sandwiches in which the chalcogen atoms are octahedral coordinated with transition metal. The atomic arrangement of bilayer CrTe₂ looks like the flower that is Dryas octopetala, each Cr atom is surrounded by eight Te atoms in figure (a). Figure c shows two patterns in the structure of MoTe₂: an armchair pattern in yellow circles and a zig-zag pattern in red circles. The optimized structural parameters of bilayer CrTe₂ and MoTe₂ are $a = b = 3.86\text{Å}$, $c = 6.20\text{Å}$ and $a = b = 3.55\text{Å}$ and $c = 14.68\text{Å}$, respectively. Mo-Te and Cr-Te bond lengths are determined to be consistently 2.709 Å and 2.746 Å, which is consistent with prior literature theoretical results.

Table-4.1 Lattice constants (\AA) a, b and c of MoTe_2 and CrTe_2 are compared.

Type	(MX_2)	a (\AA)	b (\AA)	c (\AA)
1T	CrTe_2	3.86	3.86	6.20
2H	MoTe_2	3.55	3.55	14.68

Figure-4.1 (a) Top view (b) side view of bilayer CrTe_2 (c) Top view (d) side view of MoTe_2 .

The geometry of the MoTe_2 and CrTe_2 bilayers in a single layer is such that the chalcogen atom Te along the z-axis is vertically aligned and the stacking sequence in the material is ABA. A is a chalcogen atom and B is a transition metal, and this structure looks like a sandwich (A-B-A). The transition metals Mo and Cr are merged in between two chalcogen atoms of tellurium (Te). Molybdenum/Chromium and tellurium atoms are covalently connected to each other in each layer, giving it a very high tensile strength. Weak van der Waals forces exist between the layers of the MoTe_2 and CrTe_2 bilayers.

4.2. Electronic Properties

4.2.1 Band Structure

Band structure graphs provide a visual representation of the energy levels of electrons in a material, and give us valuable information about the material's electronic properties. These graphs plot the energy levels of electrons in the material as a function wave vectors. MoTe_2 layered semimetal, exhibits metallic behavior within its planes but exhibits a bandgap in the

direction out of the plane. The band structure of CrTe₂ has predicted to have linearly dispersing electronic states, making it a Dirac semimetal. A Dirac cone created in a Dirac semimetal when the conduction and valence bands contact at specific points in the momentum space. High electron mobility brought about by this linear dispersion of electronic states makes it an attractive candidate for use in alkali-ion batteries. The observed band gap before lithiation of MoTe₂ reported to be 1.017 eV; this is quite consistent with the given results. The bilayer Chromium dichloride (CrTe₂) is zero-bandgap material; it does not have a band gap (0eV) in its electronic structure. The band gap of the materials relies upon the lithiation and after performing on both host structures, the band gap of CrTe₂ and MoTe₂ 0eV.

4.2.2 Band gap

The energy gap between the valence band (the highest occupied energy band) and the conduction band (the lowest unoccupied energy band) is an important factor in determining a material's electrical conductivity. The observed band gap of MoTe₂ reported to be 1.017 eV; this is quite consistent with the given results. This value is in the range of typical band gaps for semiconductor materials and is in the order of magnitude of several tenths of an electron volt (eV). When a semiconductor material is lithiated, the introduction of lithium ions into the material can result in the electronic structure of the material changing from that of a semiconductor to that of a metal. This change in electronic structure can result in the material exhibiting metallic behavior, such as increased conductivity and decreased resistance. The extent of this change in electronic structure and the resulting behavior can depend on the specific material and the extent of lithiation. After performing the lithiation in the host material, the band gap is 0eV of the bilayer MoTe₂. The bilayer Chromium dichloride (CrTe₂) is zero-bandgap material; it does not have a band gap in its electronic structure. Graphene (2D) also has no band gap (0eV) and commercially used electrode in lithium ion batteries. After lithiation, conductors typically do not change into another material. Lithiation refers to the process of introducing lithium ions into a material, and while this process can have an impact on the electronic structure and other properties of a material, it generally does not result in a change in the material itself. However, the presence of lithium ions can affect the conductivity of a material, as the movement of lithium ions through the material can result in changes to the distribution of charges and the overall conductivity of the material. The extent of these changes can depend on the specific material and the extent of lithiation. After performing the lithiation in the host material, the band gap is 0eV of the bilayer CrTe₂. For group 4 through group 10 TMDs, the number of d orbital electrons ranges between 0 and 6. Thorough variation in M-X-M compound, can be achieved in diversity of properties like electronic properties. Molybdenum di-telluride (MoTe₂) is a transition-metal dichalcogenides (TMD) semiconductor in which d-

electrons interactions may give rise to novel physical phenomena. Molybdenum has exceptional case in electronic configuration like tungsten (W) and Chromium (Cr) because partially filled atomic orbitals are more stable than full-filled. Transition metals (Mo) and chalcogen atom (Te) in transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) have an oxidation states are +4 and -2, respectively. Molybdenum has 6 unpaired valance electrons, one in s-orbital and five in d-orbitals. Transition metals varied the oxidation state; Molybdenum has 4+ in MoTe₂. Tellurium has 2 unpaired valance electrons in p-orbital and its oxidation state is 2-. The unit cell structure of MoTe₂ has 3 atoms, which are in triangular form. Molybdenum made double bond with tellurium on both sides. The bonding between the atoms is covalent bonding, molybdenum shares two electrons with right and left side of tellurium. We begin by reviewing the partial density of states (PDOS) of the MoTe₂ bilayer under consideration, paying special attention to the nature of the electronic states. In molybdenum (Mo), s-orbital shows least character, while the 3d-orbitals of Mo, both orbitals d_{xy} and $d_{x^2-y^2}$ show the prominent character of bonding. Other orbitals, such as d_{yz} and d_{xz} displayed same contribution in the bonding of molybdenum (Mo) and d_{z^2} shows the least participation in Mo-bonding. The PDOS graph illustrates the valance covalent bonding between s and d-orbitals from the molybdenum and p-orbital from the tellurium. These graphs also display, partial filled orbitals are more stable than full-filled orbitals. In Mo, both orbitals s and d participate in the bonding with the tellurium. Due to possible oxidation state of Mo in MoTe₂ is 4+, it made double mutual bonding with both atom of tellurium. case in electronic configuration like tungsten (W) and Chromium (Cr) because partially filled atomic orbitals are more stable than full-filled. Transition metals (Mo) and chalcogen atom (Te) in transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) have an oxidation states are +4 and -2, respectively.

Figure-4.2 Band structure diagrams of bilayer (a) CrTe₂ (b) MoTe₂ materials. The fermi level is set at 0eV.

Molybdenum made double bond with tellurium on both sides. The bonding between the atoms is covalent bonding, molybdenum shares two electrons with right and left side of tellurium. We begin by reviewing the partial density of states (PDOS) of the MoTe₂ bilayer under consideration, paying special attention to the nature of the electronic states. In molybdenum (Mo), s-orbital shows least character, while the 3d-orbitals of Mo, both orbitals d_{xy} and $d_{x^2-y^2}$ show the prominent character of bonding.

Figure-4.3 Total DOS with lithiation (a) MoTe₂ with 1Li (b) with 2 Li (c) CrTe with 1Li (d) with 2 Li.

According to the definition given in the literature, it is the amount of energy needed to assemble a crystal from its component atoms. Since it takes energy to disassemble a crystal into its component components, a positive formation energy suggests that the crystal structure is stable.

4.3. Stability of material CrTe₂

The curves of phonon dispersion presents the insight details about the stability of CrTe₂ by identifying positive phonon modes, which shows a stable crystal lattice structure of material.

The lithiation process also confirmed us the stability of material how stable it is. In particular, even after the intercalation of guest atoms (Li), the bilayer host structure is entirely unaffected. This strengthens the potential of material for use in a variety of applications and suggests a surprising degree of stability inside the material CrTe₂. A negative formation energy, on the other hand, denotes crystal instability and the potential for spontaneous breakdown. As a result, the formation energy value is crucial for material analysis and prediction. The formula of formation energy is:

$$E_{\text{form}} = \frac{E_{\text{CrTe}_2} - xE_{\text{Cr}} - yE_{\text{Te}}}{x + y} \quad (4.1)$$

Where E_{form} is the formation energy of material CrTe₂ in eV. E_{CrTe_2} , E_{Cr} , E_{Te} are the energies of host material, Cr atom and tellurium atom respectively, x and y are no of atoms in a unit cell of CrTe₂.

Figure-4.4 The phonon graph is plotted between path and frequency (THz) of CrTe₂.

A crucial variable that is frequently employ to evaluate the stability of crystal formations is formation energy. According to the definition given in the literature, it is the amount of energy needed to assemble a crystal from its component atoms. Since it takes energy to disassemble a crystal into its component components, a positive formation energy suggests that the crystal structure is stable. This is consistent with other preliminary studies that have demonstrated that a stable crystal structure requires a positive formation energy.

4.5 Stable interstitial sites

Lithiation is the foremost task to determine the stable sites for intercalation in the bilayer geometrical optimized host materials MoTe₂ and CrTe₂. The single point (SP) calculations piercing the five favorable sites for intercalation and the clue of most stable sites of bilayer materials are acquired from the literature. Table-1 displayed a negative lithiation energy corresponding to all sites of both the materials which confirms the exothermic nature of the reaction and it indicates the stability of the host material.

The first highly stable site with maximum negative lithiation energy in MoTe₂ is B_{Mo-Mo}, the lithium atom moves toward the Mo-Mo site due to high electronegativity (2.16) of Mo. In CrTe₂, the interstitial site B_{Te-Te} has higher energy in this simulation due to leading character of electronegativity (2.1) of tellurium. The reason is significant difference in electronegativity between Te and Li, the highest charge is transferred to the Te atom.

Table-4.3 Host materials 2H-Li_xMoTe₂ and Li_xT-CrTe₂ (eV/Li) on the five interstitial sites.

MoTe ₂		CrTe ₂	
Sites	Li _x MoTe ₂ (eV)	Sites	Li _x CrTe ₂ (eV)
B _{Mo}	-0.73	B _{Cr}	-0.43
B _{Mo-Te}	-0.98	B _{Cr-Te}	-0.64
B _{Te}	-0.81	B _{Te}	-1.97
B _{Te-Te}	-1.87	B _{Te-Te}	-2.9
B _{Mo-Mo}	-2.1	B _{Cr-Cr}	-2.13

These sites are positioned in between two layers diagonally ahead of each other in both host materials (Te and Mo are located at the top, bottom and in between of the hexagonal ring respectively). The second stable site for lithiation in MoTe₂ and CrTe₂ corresponds to B_{Te-Te} and B_{Cr-Cr}, which is located on intervening position of layers and both the atoms facing to each other (Te and Mo are occupying positions at the top, bottom and in between of the hexagonal ring sequentially). The third favorable sites for intercalation in MoTe₂ and CrTe₂ correspondingly to B_{Mo-Te} and B_{Cr-Te}. Because of the distinction in electronegativity between Mo and Li, B_{Mo-Te}, which is similar to B_{Cr-Te} at this location, acquires the charge towards Mo and Te from the host atoms. The next step is to calculate the lithiation energy with an increasing concentration of lithium up to three atoms in order to evaluate the storage capacity of MoTe₂ and CrTe₂ as anodes in lithium-ion batteries (Table-4). In order to achieve high-performance of lithium-ion batteries, it is essential that we are able to determine the amount of lithium that can be intercalated into the host structures and the resulting energy required.

Table-4.4 Host materials $2\text{H-Li}_x\text{MoTe}_2$ and $\text{Li}_x\text{T-CrTe}_2$ (eV/Li) on the five interstitial sites with the concentration of lithium atoms ($x=1,2,3$).

MoTe ₂			CrTe ₂				
Sites	Li _x MoTe ₂ (eV)			Sites	Li _x CrTe ₂ (eV)		
	x = 1	x = 2	x = 3		x = 1	x = 2	x = 3
B _{Mo}	-0.73	-1.6	-2.9	B _{Cr}	-0.43	-1.8	-2.9
B _{Mo-Te}	-0.98	-1.8	-2.4	B _{Cr-Te}	-0.64	-1.9	-3.2
B _{Te}	-0.81	-1.9	-2.7	B _{Te}	-1.97	-2.4	-3.9
B _{Te-Te}	-1.87	-2.1	-3.2	B _{Te-Te}	-2.9	-4.1	-5.4
B _{Mo-Mo}	-2.1	-2.8	-4.5	B _{Cr-Cr}	-2.13	-3.2	-4.2

Consequently, by figuring out lithiation energy values of these materials, we can better grasp their potential as LIB anodes and modify our approach to employing them.

4.6 Lithiation in host Structures

Up to now, we have discussed the structural and electronic properties of bilayer host materials (CrTe_2 and MoTe_2). The performance of two bilayer materials as an anode material for (LIBs) Lithium ion batteries is then compared. Before performing lithiation in bilayer materials, we must first identify the material atom with the highest electronegativity and placed the lithium atom near that atom. There are two advantages: one is that the lithium atom will transfer the valence electron to the host material of the structure and will be stable at that site; the other is that it lowers the possibility of repulsion and deformation of the structure. The lithiation in the host material MoTe_2 as shown in figure-2. One by one increased the concentration of Li atoms in the bilayers of the host materials to determine theoretical storage capacity (TSC) and actual storage capacity (ASC). Firstly, we tested the MoTe_2 as a benchmark, completing the lithiation on it. When the first lithium atom ($x = 1$) intercalates into a bilayer of MoTe_2 , the lithiation energy is negative. The material has the capability to adsorb the lithium atoms. After performing this task 4–5 times, when we intercalate a 6th atom of lithium ($x = 6$), the lithiation energy gets positive. It means the material has no capacity to absorb more lithium atoms. We perform these calculations 2–3 times to be satisfied with the results, which are in excellent accord with the stated theoretical and experimental results.

The lithiation energy can be determined with the help of this equation.

$$E_{\text{Li}} = E_{\text{Li}_x\text{MoTe}_2} - xE_{\text{Li}} - E_{\text{MoTe}_2} \quad (4.2)$$

Where $E_{\text{Li}_x\text{MoTe}_2}$ is the lithiation energy (eV) of Li in MoTe_2 , E_{Li} is geometrical optimized energy of Lithium (where x indicates the of Lithium atoms) and E_{MoTe_2} is energy of

geometrical optimized MoTe₂ structure. In lithium-ion batteries, the redox (reduction-oxidation) reaction refers to the transfer of electrons between the two electrodes, the anode and the cathode. The anode, usually made of graphite (commercially used-3D material), loses electrons (oxidation) and the cathode, usually made of a lithium compound, gains electrons (reduction). This transfer of electrons creates a flow of ions from the cathode to the anode, creating a flow of electrical current. When the battery is charged, lithium ions are attracted to the anode, where they are oxidized and release electrons, while the cathode gains electrons, reducing the lithium ions. During discharge, the process is reversed, with the lithium ions being reduced at the cathode and oxidized at the anode, generating an electrical current. This redox reaction is the basic mechanism that allows lithium-ion batteries to store and release electrical energy. The redox reaction of this material is that:

By experimental reported results, 4 lithium atoms intercalated in the host structure of 2H-MoTe₂ and its theoretical capacity is 305.3mAhg⁻¹. This redox reaction is important when we study the electrochemical process or we checking the whole mechanism of battery. But now, we are just working on the anode of the lithium ion batteries. In order to determine storage capacity, we steadily raised the Li atom concentration in between the bilayers of host material (MoTe₂). In order to occupy the stable position, Li atoms are optimised and given the chance to interact with MoTe₂ layers. The reaction's nature is monitored using the predicted optimal energy values, which are also utilized to calculate the lithiation energy at various Li concentrations. As Li concentration increased, the interlayer gap did not considerably widen, demonstrating the host structure's capacity to maintain volume. The reaction is exothermic until the concentration of Lithium atoms is 4. Our lithiation energy is positive and reaction is endothermic when intercalate the 5th atom of lithium (x = 5) in the host structure of a material as shown in graph-1. Theoretical capacity can be calculated through this formula, by using equation (2.2).

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{n * F}{M_{\text{MoTe}_2}}$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = \frac{4 * 26.801}{351.1} \times 1000$$

$$\text{Theoretical Capacity} = 305 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$$

In comparison, the theoretical storage capacities (TCS) of bilayer (2H-MoTe₂) reported and calculated are 305.3 mAhg⁻¹ and 381.6 mAhg⁻¹, which agree well with previous theoretical results. We moved on to testing a new material as an anode in lithium ion batteries after

completing all calculations on benchmark material (MoTe_2). The supercell (4x4) of bilayer CrTe_2 is optimised for a stable position and allowed to intercalate the lithium atoms into the host structure.

Figure 4.5 The lithiated host structure of bilayer CrTe_2 and MoTe_2

Figure 4.6 The graph is plotted between the x (Li) concentration of lithium and lithiation energy (Li/eV) for comparison between bilayer CrTe_2 and MoTe_2 .

4.7 Migration Path of Lithium atoms

The calculation of NEB determines the diffusion energy barrier that is inversely proportional to diffusion rate and gives us valuable information about the charging and discharging rate of battery. The migration paths of lithium into the bilayer host material CrTe_2 must be examined

deeper into in order to gain a better understanding of the lithiation and delithiation processes. Lithium experiences an energy barrier as it passes through the layers of host material structure that has been computed and calculated. The energy needed for lithium to migrate between the layers of host structure, which is crucial for lithium-ion battery charging efficiency and is greatly influenced by this transition barrier. Five distinct pathways have been evaluated to determine the energy losses and the lowest diffusion barrier. The calculations have been carried out using CI-NEB. We tested a novel material CrTe_2 diffusion path in order to understand its insights into the diffusion process. Five different transition pathways have been considered in our simulation, one of which is along the x-axis, y-axis and three along z-axis. These transition paths are vital to understanding the migration patterns of Li ions in the host material. We can enhance the functionality of lithium-ion batteries and gain a better understanding of the energy constraints at play by looking at these pathways. We have five intermediate images for each case to ensure accuracy that are: (1) the middle hexagonal ring on the upper layer to the middle of the hexagonal ring on the lower layer (both the rings are in row wise ahead positions along x-axis) (2) Amidst top hexagonal ring to the middle of the hexagonal ring along y-axis.

Figure 4.7 These graphs are plot between reaction path and energy for path-1 and path-2 for both materials CrTe_2 and MoTe_2 .

The first migration path entails from middle hexagonal ring on the upper layer to the middle of the hexagonal ring on the lower layer along x-axis with barrier energy value 0.57 eV. When the concentration of lithium is lower, the highly favorable and stable site is center of hexagonal ring. The bridging between two hexagonal rings creates the least amount of energy needed for Li to diffuse into a stable position. In this pathway, the interacting Li atom is near to Te atom. The lithium atom transfers maximum charge to the tellurium atom is indicted by Hirschfield charge analysis. The second migration path is between from top hexagonal ring to the middle of the hexagonal ring along y-axis and this has third highest energy barrier value 0.49 eV. This transition path is suitable to some extent for lithiation. The third migration path is longer migration path along z-axis from top layer of middle hexagonal ring to the lower layer of bottom hexagonal ring and has energy barrier value is 1.98 eV. This path discloses that Li atoms finds it

extremely challenging to follow this path because the transition barrier requires the higher energy to overcome. The second migration path is between from top hexagonal ring to the middle of the hexagonal ring along y-axis and this has third highest energy barrier value 0.49 eV. This transition path is suitable to some extent for lithiation. The third migration path is longer migration path along z-axis from top layer of middle hexagonal ring to the lower layer of bottom hexagonal ring and has energy barrier value is 1.98 eV. This path discloses that Li atoms finds it extremely challenging to follow this path because the transition barrier requires the higher energy to overcome. The lithium atom transfers maximum charge to the tellurium atom is indicted by Hirschfield charge analysis. The fifth shorter migration path along z-axis that initiate from left side of lower layer of first triangular ring (Te-Cr-Te) to the left side of upper layer. This is the second-smallest energy diffusion barrier value is 0.32 eV. There is more space for Li to diffuse inside the layers, which is an added benefit of this path. The second, fourth and fifth path is preferable for intercalation and depletion of lithium atoms in host structure material CrTe₂.

Figure 4.8 Migration paths of both host structures (a) x-axis view of CrTe₂ (b) MoTe₂ (c) z-axis view of CrTe₂ (d) MoTe₂.

4.8 Electron localized filed (ELF)

A powerful tool ELF is used to analyzing chemical bonding character and provides valuable information about which electron localized or delocalized within a material. A value 0 on scale set indicates delocalization and 1 is localization. In general, metallic bonding indicative of low degree of localization of electron (delocalization) and its ELF value is round about 0.5. The covalent bonding demonstrates the higher degree of electron localization due to sharing of

electrons between atoms around specific nuclei and results the value of ELF is greater than metallic bonding (>0.5). Ionic bonds formed through the interaction of the negatively charged Cr or Te ions in the host structure with the positively charged T (Te or Li) ions. Covalent bonding develops as a result of the sharing electrons between Cr and Te atoms, forming a network of covalent bonds. figure-8 (c). The lithiated host structure of CrTe_2 that demonstrates a bonding character that comprises metallic, ionic, and covalent bonding as well as orbital hybridization. The delocalized electrons in the metal (Cr) atoms, which occupy hybridized d-orbitals and produce a sea of electrons that hold the atoms together, are what cause metallic bonding. The transport of electrons between various orbitals causes ionic bonding between the negatively charged Te ions and the positively charged Li ions in the host structure. The Cr and Te atoms share electrons that leading to covalent bonding, which made possible by the hybridization of orbitals. In particular, the hybridized orbitals overlap causes covalent bonds to form throughout the entire host structure CrTe_2 . The stability and properties of material enhanced by the combination of these various bonding types and orbital hybridization.

Figure 4.9 (a) ELF map of pristine material MoTe_2 (b) lithiated MoTe_2 (c) pristine material CrTe_2 (d) lithiated host material CrTe_2 .

4.9 Hirshfeld Charge Analysis

Hirshfeld analysis was employed to quantify the charge transfer between lithium and Mo/CrTe₂ host structure, which is crucial for studying the electrochemical performance of lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). The Cr layer positioned between two layers of Te atoms composes the structure of CrTe₂. The Te atoms have a valence electron configuration of 5s²5p⁴ and oxidation state is -2, while the Mo/Cr atoms have a valence electron configuration of 5s²4d⁵/3d⁵4s¹ and oxidation state is +4. A charge transfer occurs between the Te atom -0.024e and Cr atom 0.036e, indicating a flow of electrons from the Te atom to the Mo atom. This charge transfer suggests a partially ionic character in the Mo-Te bonds. This causes a charge transfer from the Te atom -0.036e to the Cr atom 0.090e, the Cr-Te bonds indicates a partially metallic character. The Cr and Te atoms are anticipated accepting electrons from the Li ions, leaving the Li ions with a net negative charge while the Cr and Te atoms have a net positive charge. The precise amount of charge transfer will be determined by the individual oxidation states of Cr and Te atoms and concentration of Li atoms intercalated into host structure material. The Te atoms have a higher electronegativity than Cr atoms, lithium is typically anticipated to transfer the maximum charge -0.032 to them. In this analysis of CrTe₂, host structure after lithiation containing up to 21 lithium atoms were considered, as they exhibit the same charge transfer mechanism.

Figure 4.10 Hirshfeld Analysis charge (a) pristine MoTe₂ (b) Lithiated MoTe₂ (c) pristine CrTe₂ (d) Lithiated CrTe₂.

The results presented in Table 2 demonstrate that a plus sign indicates the loss of electrons in each system with varying numbers of lithium atoms. To assess the rate of lithium transfer towards Mo/Cr and Te atoms, the charge transfer was calculated for the top sites of these atoms. When lithium is positioned on the top site of Cr/Mo, the calculated charge transfer is e, while on the top site of Tellurium, it is 0.121e. The greater electron transfer towards carbon can be attributed

to its higher electronegativity, making lithium more stable in its vicinity due to substantial charge transfer. As the number of intercalated lithium atoms increases, the charge transfer towards the layered structure becomes more pronounced. The Te atoms have a higher electronegativity than Cr atoms, lithium is typically anticipated to transfer the maximum charge -0.032 to them. In this analysis of CrTe₂, host structure after lithiation containing up to 21 lithium atoms were considered, as they exhibit the same charge transfer mechanism.

4.10 Diffusion co-efficient and ionic conductivity

Diffusion coefficient is an important parameter for designing of new anode materials. We performed MD at temperature range 300 to 1600K to analyze the diffusion coefficient of CrTe₂. This simulation helps us understand how lithium atoms move through anode material in batteries and temperature-dependent behavior of diffusivity plays a crucial role to study their transport properties. For instance, if guest atoms (Li-atoms) in the host material disturbs the layered structure this could result in decreased ionic conductivity σ and effects of these faults on the overall performance of battery by simulating the diffusion of guest atoms in the presence of such defects. However, depending on the temperature range investigated and specifications such as the force field selection and length may need to be alter. The diffusion coefficient of Li-atoms in host material CrTe₂ is determined using the mean square displacement (MSD) of particles over time. This Einstein relation used to get the diffusion coefficient from the MSD.

$$\text{MSD} = \langle |R_{\text{Li}}(t) - R_{\text{Li}}(0)|^2 \rangle \quad (4.4)$$

The diffusion co-efficient D_{Li^+} formula is:

$$D_{\text{Li}^+} = \frac{\langle \text{MSD} \rangle}{6t} = \frac{\langle |R_{\text{Li}}(t) - R_{\text{Li}}(0)|^2 \rangle}{6t} \quad (4.5)$$

The Li ion position at time “t” represented by $R_{\text{Li}}(t)$ and the ensemble average during the MD simulation time shown in angle brackets. The value of diffusion co-efficient (D_{Li}) and ionic conductivity of CrTe₂ at room temperature 300K is $4.48 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ and $5.85 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Scm}^{-1}$. The diffusivity of Li atoms in host material CrTe₂ is higher than MoTe₂ ($3.83 \times 10^{-15} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$), commercially used anode materials graphite ($10^{-14} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$), graphene ($10^{-10} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$), Si (3.8×10^{-13}) and its derivatives silicene, g-CSi₂. [1, 17, 72-74]. The Arrhenius equation takes into account the diffusion coefficient (D) of the Li cation on the CrTe₂ for the diffusion properties.

$$D(T) = D_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{K_B T}\right) \quad (4.6)$$

Figure-4.11 The diffusion Co-efficient of CrTe₂ is calculate by Arrhenius equation at different temperatures.

CONCLUSIONS

In this comprehensive study, we conducted a systematic analysis using first principles calculations to assess the potential of CrTe_2 as an anode material for lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). By calculating the lithiation energy for seven high symmetry intercalation sites, we determined that the site known as "X" exhibited the most favorable characteristics, with the lowest intercalation energy recorded at 0.34 eV and theoretical capacity 1758 mAhg^{-1} . To overcome this limitation, we explored the creation of defects and vacancies within CrTe_2 -like materials. Introducing non-stoichiometric conditions, we found that even with such modifications, the energy reactions remained endothermic. To address this, we conducted calculations specifically focusing on Chromium, which provided sufficient space for lithium accommodation in layered CrTe_2 , allowing for the inclusion of up to two lithium atoms in Li. Moreover, our study involved an analysis of lithium diffusion pathways. Overall, this first principles-based study provides valuable insights into the potential use of silicon carbide as an anode material in lithium-ion batteries. The findings contribute to a better understanding of the lithiation process, lithium diffusion, and thermal stability, facilitating the design and development of advanced LIBs with improved performance and safety features.

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APPENDIX-01

Abbreviation used in the Thesis		
Sr #	Item	Abbreviation
1.	Lithium ion batteres	LIBs
2.	Sodium ion Batteries	NIBs
3.	Potassium ion batteries	KIBs
4.	Theoretical storage capacity	TCS
5.	Diffusion Co-effcient	DC
6.	Electric Vehicles	EVs
7.	Transition metal dichalocogenides	TMDCs
8.	Transition metal oxides	TMOs
9.	Transition metal carbonates	TMCs
10.	Nudged Elastic Band	NEB
11.	Electron localized field	ELF
12.	Multivalent ion batteries	MVBs
13.	Monovalent ion batteries	MIVBs
14.	Secondary batteries	SB
15.	Lithium titanate oxide	LTO
16.	Iron oxide	FeO
17.	Stronisium rutnate oxide	SRO

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